

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D4.8 Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts - update M33

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Executive Summary

The systematic and targeted in-depth research with the utilization of interdisciplinary academic lenses to examine the multi-dimensional phenomenon of the COVID-19 pandemic is part of the unique characteristics of the COVINFORM project. The consortium of the project provides an in-depth examination and analysis of the pandemic, emphasizing on the behavioural and socio-economic impact relating to the COVID-19 pandemic. Whereas WP4, scrutinizes governmental structures, crisis management responses, pandemic preparedness plans and mechanisms that have been altered or were completely abolished. As well as, COVID-19 policies and practices, as well as lessons learned and recommendations that can be drawn for a potential future healthcare crisis of equal or similar scale. The current deliverable (D4.8) Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts - update M33 of Work Package 4 (WP4: Government responses and impact assessment), is the second iteration of Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts (D4.4), mainly focusing on synthesizing data that is drawn from WP4 desktop and empirical research. The synthesis of governmental responses impacts and subsequently the documentation of lessons learned can be achieved by interpreting the analysis of governmental responses, structural alterations and studying the evolution of policies and practices. In addition, it is important to examine their relevant adaptations to increase their efficiency and effectiveness against the COVID-19 pandemic. The current deliverable examines the analysis conducted in D4.7 (Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment - update M32), and utilises D4.5 (Baseline report: Governmental responses - updated M22) and D4.6 (Research design: Governmental responses - update M26) which lay the foundation for the synthesis and lessons learned on governmental responses and impacts. This deliverable mainly emphasizes on interpreting the data and analysis which was conducted in April 2022 until July 2023. It also builds on the data collected prior to that, specifically in relation to D4.1 and D4.3 but with a focus on documenting the main findings, lessons learned and subsequently proceeds to the production of recommendations for governmental officials and decision makers, practitioners and academics among relevant stakeholders on European, national, regional and local scope who have an active role in engaging with governmental response mechanism against the COVID-19 pandemic.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease
D	Deliverable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EU	European Union
ICU	Intensive Care Unit
NPIs	Non-pharmaceutical interventions
UK	United Kingdom
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package
DGS	Directorate General of Health
ANPC	National Civil Protection Authority
PHA	Public Health Authority
CCS	Civil Contingencies Secretariat
NHS	National Health Service

1 Introduction

On 5 May 2023 the Director General of UN World Health Organization (WHO) Dr. Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus, declared that COVID-19 has ceased to be characterized as a global health emergency (WHO, 2023)¹. The Director General nevertheless highlighted that governmental systems and actors should avoid reassurance and subsequently opt-out from dismantling or neglecting the governmental response mechanisms. Instead, implementing policies and practices was encouraged, underlining the imminent threat that the risk of infections and emergence of new variants which are likely to initiate a cascading chain of events of contemporary surges in COVID-19 infections and deaths (ibid).

In compliance with the famous quotation provided by philosopher George Santayana “those who cannot remember the past are condemned to repeat it” (1910), Dr. Ghebreyesus who has a central administrative and decision making role against healthcare related disasters such as the COVID-19 pandemic, has underlined that nations and governmental actors should demonstrate vigilance and awareness whilst recommending to invest in the sustainability of socio-economic and healthcare systems that have been built and fortified as a response to COVID-19 (WHO, 2023)². In the aforementioned press release, Dr. Ghebreyesus reminded the governmental decisions and sacrifices the global community have made. The press release also stressed the need to learn the lessons that the pandemic has been trying to teach. According to the Director General “If we all go back to how things were before COVID-19, we will have failed to learn our lessons, and we will have failed future generations. This experience must change us all for the better” (WHO, 2023).

The overarching issues that are presented in the COVINFORM research project and addressed in WP4, are to identify the underlying patterns in the governmental structure, mechanism and response system and document alterations in the implementation of measures through practices and policies in the target countries. To do so, WP4 proceeds to examine the nature of the governmental structures, means and methods that the governmental response mechanism and actors have implemented. To address the social-economic, legal and cultural factors that have impacted the social context by reviewing, describing, conducting empirical research and in-depth analysis, which subsequently will lead to the synthesis of main findings, lessons learned and recommendations.

WP4 main objectives are:

- To conduct a review and describe the governmental structures and responses on a national level in the 15 project target countries, as well as on a regional/local level in selected sub-national research sites and case studies which is fulfilled in D4.1 and D4.5.
- To carry out primary empirical research among governmental stakeholders and policy experts in the 10 sub-national research sites and perform an in-depth analysis of key dimensions of governmental response impact in the project target countries:
 - I. Pandemic planning and preparedness.
 - II. Governmental approaches to vulnerability.
 - III. Responses on multiple levels of governance.
 - IV. Economic and social welfare responses and socio-political, legal, and ethical factors influencing governmental responses.

The primary empirical research and in-depth analysis is presented in D4.3 and D4.7.

D4.4 and D4.8, utilizing data drawn from the aforementioned deliverables, aims to synthesize research findings on governmental responses and impacts in a complex systems framework (see D3.2) and

¹ <https://www.who.int/news-room/speeches/item/who-director-general-s-opening-remarks-at-the-media-briefing--5-may-2023>.

² <https://news.un.org/en/story/2023/05/1136367>.

prepare recommendations and other inputs for WP8. In particular, D4.4 examines the timeframe between January 2020 until April 2022, whereas D4.8 examines the timeframe between April 2022 until July 2023.

This deliverable will synthesize and interpret the findings of D4.5 – D4.7 from an interdisciplinary and intersectional perspective, within the theoretical framework established in WP2 and WP3. D4.8 is structured by emphasizing on the synthesis and interpretation of findings which lead to the production of lessons learned and recommendations. The lessons learned and recommendations are intended to be utilized by governmental officials, decision makers and policy experts, academia and practitioners within the governmental mechanism.

The overarching research questions which are examined in D4.8 include the following:

- RQ1: How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practiced?
- RQ2: How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?
- RQ3: What are the different kinds of barriers encountered in the pandemic response and how were they managed?
- RQ4: What are the main lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse social European environments?

In detail, the section of synthesis will provide a compilation of lessons learned, emphasizing mainly on both successful and unsuccessful policies and practices that were identified in the target countries, leading to structured recommendations in relation to the most effective courses of action as part of the governmental mechanism response. The last section will summarize the main research findings and main concluding remarks, as well as potential limitations or caveats.

WP4 is considered a core work package of significant importance for the COVINFORM project, as it conducts an in-depth examination of governmental systems, actors, response mechanisms, implemented measures, policies and practices, subsequently and inevitably, directly influencing healthcare systems (WP5 - *Public Health responses and impact assessment*), community actors and grassroots initiatives (WP6 - *Citizen and community responses and impact assessment*) as well as communication experts and communication crisis management (WP7 - *Inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation*).

This deliverable provides a brief overview of the scope, research activities and timeline that relate to D4.8. The introduction of D4.8, which subsequently is presented later, provides a more in-depth overview of research activities, brief timeline of contemporary COVID-19 events, main objectives and research questions, as well as the scope of D4.8. The methodological section elaborates the methodological aspect of the research activities conducted within the context of D4.8, highlights the importance of the Socio-ecological system framework in which this deliverable has emphasized on, whilst reiterating the main research questions of the COVINFORM project. Moreover, the methodology section also adopts a retrospective lens examining how all WP4 deliverables are linked and the scope of each WP4 deliverable. In addition, the following section, conducts an analysis and elaborates on *Good practices, lessons learned and synthesis of recommendations*, of each target country in three distinct time frames (prior to the pandemic until the outbreak - T0, Pandemic outbreak until the roll out of the vaccines - T1, rollout of the vaccines until the current period of time - T3), and introduces three thematic areas (governmental responses and preparedness, changes on policies and practices, vulnerability). Comparative analysis is utilised within this section in a subtler manner, in order to avoid overshadowing the identification of good practices, lessons learned and the synthesis of recommendations, which are also summarised in the section of *Conclusion*, separating the main findings of the document in three phases of the pandemic (T0, T1 and T2), simultaneously presenting a specialized section of discussion concerning *vulnerability*. Additionally, Annex 1 presents a table with

the cross-country indicators also provided in the country frames, in three moments in time, as collected for the dashboard.

2 Methodology

The section of methodology of D4.8: Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts - update M33 will include an in-depth presentation of the core component which is cross country comparative analysis of the different governmental structures and the changes that occurred during the period of time that D4.8 examines. The main objective of D4.8 is to interpret and synthesize data which contribute towards the identification of main findings and lessons learned, particularly emphasizing in the documentation of good practices and policies relating to the governmental response mechanism and pandemic management of COVID-19. Specifically, contrary to the predecessor of this deliverable, D4.4, which examined governmental structures, responses, policies, practices and adaptations between January 2020 and April 2022, the current deliverable (D4.8 - Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts - update M33) introduces a methodological change of course and examines the following timeframe: April 2022 until July 2023, while incorporating data documented in D4.4 as a foundation at the core of methodology. In addition, the unique characteristic of D4.8 is the inclusion of the methodological framework that is utilized in D4.7 (Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment - update M32), presenting and thoroughly examining three distinct pandemic phases (Model T0: Baseline pre-COVID-19 pandemic), (Model T1: T1: Pandemic outbreak to vaccination), (Model T2: T2: Post-vaccination). This approach will allow D4.8 to conduct the synthesis of main findings and lessons learned in a more concrete manner, highlighting good practices which relate to policies and practices of the COVID-19 governmental response mechanism.

To summarise, D4.8 conducts an overview and analysis of the acquired data which is separated on three distinct phases (T0, T1, T3), and three thematic areas (governmental responses and preparedness, changes on policies and practices, vulnerability). The analysis of data within D4.8, allows the identification of lessons learned and subsequently the drafting of recommendations, based on a comparison between responses, policies, practices and overall approach towards COVID-19, between the COVINFORM countries.

According to Drobnič (2014) *“the goal of comparative analysis is to search for similarity and variance among units of analysis. Comparative research commonly involves the description and explanation of similarities and differences of conditions or outcomes among large-scale social units, usually regions, nations, societies, and cultures.”* (Drobnič, 2014)³. Based on this definition, comparative analysis within the context and main methodological framework of COVINFORM is the comparison of specific units of analysis, in this case governmental response mechanism, policies and practices, across the specified target countries. Cross country comparative analysis aims to capture the similarities and differences with respect to the variables that are analysed.

Furthermore, D4.8 is also driven by the main overarching research questions of the COVINFORM project:

- RQ1: How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted and practiced?

³ https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007/978-94-007-0753-5_492#Sec31149.

- RQ2: How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?
- RQ3: What were the different kinds of barriers encountered in the pandemic response and how were they managed?
- RQ4: What are the lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?
 - Practices
 - Policies

Within the context of this research project, at least five interviews with governmental officials, such as decision makers and policy experts, particularly on a national and regional as well as local administrative level, that have a direct affiliation with the pandemic management and governmental response were conducted in each target country. The main context of the interviews aimed at identifying and examining the governmental approach, structure and responses of the pandemic mechanism in each participant country as well as identifying effective, efficient practices and policies. One of the main limitations of this deliverable is the inability to acquire, limited to the public information, which may further elaborate on contributing factors which assisted in the adoption and implementation of specific policies and practices in each target country.

3 Good practices, lessons learned and synthesis of recommendations

3.1 Baseline conditions: governmental structures prior to the COVID-19 pandemic (T0)

Governmental structure and COVID-19 crisis response system in Austria

On a national level, **Austria** has abided by the federal parliamentary democracy model. The country is divided into nine provinces, whose governments have great autonomy and respect for the principles of representative democracy. That means that the power is exercised by the federal government, at national level, and by local governments, at local level. Austria's executive, federal branch consists of the head of state, the head of government (Chancellor) and the Federal Cabinet. The main legislative body in Austria is National Assembly alongside the Federal Council, which is the representation of the Provinces in the Parliament and has its members chosen by the Provincial Assemblies of its respected province. Finally, regarding the Judicial Branch is independent from the other two branches and is responsible for the fair application of the Law in all Austrian territory⁴. Austria in comparison to other COVINFORM countries, had a fragmented administrative approach.

The main **good practices** were that Austria relied on the pre-existing Epidemic legislation (Migration.Gv, n.d.)⁵ (with some articles reformed due to COVID-19) and the Katastrophenhilfe Gesetz (law for combatting catastrophes) (Bundministerium Inneres, n.d.)⁶ (Nimmervoll, 2020). Specifically, Austria has the Epidemiegesetz (Epidemic Law), which however was last updated in 1950,

⁴ Migration. Gv. (n.d.). The political, administrative and legal systems. Available at:

<https://www.migration.gv.at/en/living-and-working-in-austria/austria-at-a-glance/the-political-administrative-and-legal-systems/>.

⁵ Republik Österreich. (1950). Epidemiegesetz. Bundesgesetzblatt für die Republik Österreich. Available at:

https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblPdf/1950_186_0/1950_186_0.pdf.

⁶ Bundministerium Inneres. (n.d.). Krisen- und Katastrophenmanagement. Available at:

<https://www.bmi.gv.at/204/skkm/start.aspx>.

consequently creating an imperative need for an update utilising contemporary data. This was the base for the pandemic management in early 2020, and the document which outlines that the Health Ministry oversees the pandemic response. Of particular importance was the influenza Pandemic Plan (Influenza Pandemieplan – Strategie für Österreich), which includes a strategy for the country to cope with the Influenza virus. The document was published in 2006 by the former Federal Ministry for Women and Health and is still in use today (Austrian Parliament, 2022)⁷.

Furthermore, as a **good practice**, a pre-existing body also acted, as a response named “Austrian National Crisis and Catastrophe Emergency Task Force”⁸, which has a supporting role towards the federal states and a monitoring role of the crisis. The SKKM is an event-driven task force which only becomes active in times of crisis. It is located within the Ministry of Interior and is an institution that supports the federal states that are mainly in charge of reacting to situations of crisis and catastrophe. It consists of representatives of each of the ministries as well as states, operational organisations (such as police, etc.) and media outlets.

Governmental structure and COVID-19 crisis response system in Belgium

Belgium is a constitutional representative monarchy, where the king is the Head of State (Belgium.be, n.d.)⁹. The executive branch of Belgium consists of the Head of Government (Prime Minister) and the Council of Ministers, as well as the State Secretaries which do not attend the Council (Belgian Constitution, n.d.)¹⁰. The country is divided in five regions; whose governments have great autonomy. On a local level the governments of these five Belgian “federated entities” differentiate from the central one in terms of responsibilities. A prime example is the Federal Government that is in charge for the framework and the programs of the hospitals whereas the Local ones for certain health services and hospital accreditation standards (Vandijck & Annemans 2010). Legislation-wise, the main body responsible is the Chamber of Representatives and its members are elected via representative elections¹¹. Each of these five regions or (federal entities) have their own parliament or unicameral council, which can vote decrees with the same legal power as the Central one¹². Similar to Austria and Germany, Belgium emphasized in a fragmented administrative approach, providing enhanced autonomy in federal, regional states.

The main **good practice** in Belgium is the fact that prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, Belgium already had a crisis management structure for potential pandemics. In Belgium, no state of emergency was declared, which is due to the unconstitutionality of the suspension of all rights in the country. Governmental response was based on a ‘consultation structure’ existing and newly created bodies.

Additionally, Belgium had set up a National Focal Point (NFP) over the course of 2007 and 2008, which is responsible for coordinating the analysis of national public health events, as well as for communication with the contact points. Besides the NFP, the Belgian monitoring and risk management

⁷ https://www.parlament.gv.at/dokument/XXVII/III/658/imfname_1450246.pdf.

⁸ Supra note 6.

⁹ Belgium.de. (n.d.). The structure of the Federal State and the power levels. Available at: https://www.belgium.be/en/about_belgium/government/federale_staat/structure.

¹⁰ The Constitution. (n.d.). On the King and the Federal Government. Available at: <https://web.archive.org/web/20100403214530/http://www.fed-parl.be/gwuk0006.htm#E11E6>.

¹¹ Ibid.

¹² Belgium.de. (n.d.). The structure of the Federal State and the power levels. Available at: https://www.belgium.be/en/about_belgium/government/federale_staat/structure.

system has two other main actors: The Risk Assessment Group (RAG) and the Risk Management Group (RMG), which analyses the risk to the population based on epidemiological and scientific data and RAG provides advice to the RMG, and the RMG then uses this advice to decide on public health measures (FPS Health, 2018). The existence of the aforementioned entities and the work can be considered as a good practice, as these bodies actively supported decision making and governmental responses based on the analysis of epidemiological data. This led the adoption of more targeted and effective responses.

Governmental structure and COVID-19 crisis response system in Germany

Germany's political system is the federal parliamentary democracy. Germany, in comparison to other countries, had a fragmented administrative authority and approach towards crisis management in each region. The executive power is exercised by the Federal President, the Federal Chancellor and the Cabinet (The Federal Government, n.d.)¹³. The President, who is the head of State mainly has a ceremonial role. This means that their duties are to represent the Federal Republic of Germany in matters of international Law and to sign all federal laws before they can be applied. On a national level, the executive branch is comprised of the Federal Chancellor, acting as Head of Government and being the main controller of government decisions. The number and composition of his/her cabinet are determined by him and her has the power to appoint a Deputy with the unofficial capacity of the Vice-Chancellor. The legislative authority of Germany is the national parliament (Bundestag) and the federal council (Bundesrat) which has the authority to influence the decision-making process (veto) in order to ensure a relative political balance. On a regional level Germany has 16 states (Landers) that are administrative autonomous and have a similar political structure to the Federal one. The abovementioned states are essential in the German institutional structure as they manage their own decisions made by a Head of Government and his Cabinet, while having their own state parliaments (Landtag). These regional authorities receive regulation in areas such as education, education, culture, infrastructure, daily administrative issues, and internal security within the area of responsibility¹⁴.

In relation to Germany's crisis response system prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, Germany had the 2017 National Pandemic Plan, a successor to an earlier pandemic plan launched in 2005. The National Pandemic Plan, updated in March 2020, includes pandemic governance, medical responses, and non-pharmaceutical interventions such as reporting, diagnosis, hygiene, social distancing and other behaviour modification measures, protective clothing, disinfection measures, and information and risk communication (RKI, 2017, p. 26). Furthermore, it specifies that in the event of health emergencies, a joint Federal Ministry of Health (BMG) and Federal Ministry of the Interior, Building and Community (BMI) task force (Krisenstab BMI/BMG) should be formed.

The main lesson learned which is identified in **Germany** prior to and during the outbreak of the pandemic (T0), is that Germany did not declare a State of Emergency. As its Governmental responses to COVID-19 were based on its pre-existing Infection Protection Act (Infektionsschutzgesetz -- IfSG), National Pandemic Plan, and other relevant laws and guidelines. Several restrictions were decided by the Federal Government but executed by the Lander ones. This contributed to the fact that

¹³ The Federal Government. (n.d.) Structure and Tasks. Available at: <https://www.bundesregierung.de/breg-en/federal-government/structure-and-tasks-470508>.

¹⁴ Ibid.

depending on the extent of the pandemic each state functioned individually to meet its needs, which can be considered as a **good practice** for countries abiding to a fragmented governance system.

Governmental structure and COVID-19 crisis response system in Greece

The socio-governmental foundation of **Greece** is based on Presidential Parliamentary Republic, which is based on the Constitution of 1975 as revised in 1986, 2001, 2008 and 2019 (Hellenic Parliament, n.d.). In comparison to the aforementioned countries, Greece had a top-down, central administrative authority and crisis management approach. According to the Constitution, the Head of State is the President, who is elected every 5 years by the Parliament (Presidency of the Hellenic Republic, n.d.). While the President of Government, is the Prime Minister, who is the second-in-class state institution, following the President of the Republic. Who is the true administrative power, and is elected by the people every 4 years (Hellenic Republic the Prime Minister, 2021). The government consists of the Council of Ministers and the government Council for Foreign and Defense Affairs (KYSEA), while the former comprises 19 Ministries (Hellenic Republic, 2021b). The legislative power is exercised by Parliament and the President of the Republic, while the executive power is exercised by the President of the Republic and the Government, with the judicial power being laid upon the relevant courts (Hellenic Parliament, n.d.). Regarding the regional level there are 13 administrative regions and 74 prefectures, while all of them are subdivided to 325 municipalities (Patridognosia, n.d.).

The main lesson learned which is identified in Greece prior and during the outbreak of the pandemic (T0), is that the centralized governance administrative system, did not experience any serious adaptations or changes in the governmental structure (Council of Europe, n.d.). This could be identified mainly to constitutional limitations which do not allow extreme structural changes in emergencies and crises during peacetime, but also the unwillingness of the government to practice such measures. Moreover, based on our expert interviews, during this phase, Greece was lacking a clear response mechanism and crisis management structure, with overall oversight of the situation, while experienced several challenges in relation to the integration of the many relevant stakeholders, in order to construct and conduct an effective COVID-19 response.

The general lack of authority transferred in regional and local areas by the central government in Greece, may have been a contributing factor which impacted the organization, structure and crisis management response. The centralization approach of the Greek government can be seen, in the more than 800 Acts of legislative content (Laws, Joint Ministerial decisions, Ministerial decision, Decrees etc.), imposed in the Greek territory, declaring the country in a state of emergency, regulating all the administrative, financial educational, labor, religious, insurance, migration related aspects of the Greek society, by adopting in general strict measures (International Monetary Fund, n.d.).

Regarding the crisis response measures, another main lesson learned, is that those adopted by the Greek government had a substantial impact on the everyday lives of all the citizens, since they were restrictive, applied immediately after the beginning of the appearance of COVID-19 pandemic in the Greek territory, through curfew limitations, lockdowns (local and/or national), restrictions to movements and travelling, quarantines, limitation of public or private social gatherings, mandatory use of face masks indoors and outdoors, etc., with both sociological/psychological and financial impact (A3M, n.d.). However, the Greek government announced certain financial benefits and/or tax and VAT releases for small and medium-sized businesses especially for sectors that had been impacted the most by the measures, as well as individuals (European Commission, n.d.). Interesting enough, all official

governmental announcements were translated into the main languages spoken in the country, while considering the practice of religions, ceremonies, rituals, and gatherings, these are allowed if specific requirements are met and under strict circumstances, showing tolerance to minorities (Hellenic Ministry of Migration and Asylum, n.d.).

Governmental structure and COVID-19 crisis response system in Italy

The political system in **Italy** is a decentralised democratic parliamentary Republic comprising a three-way division of power. The Council of Ministers is the exercising body of the Executive power. The State also exercises control over 15 ordinary regions and four regions and two provinces with special autonomy under specific constitutional limitations¹⁵. The regional government consists of the Regional council which has constitutionally limited legislative powers, the regional committee with executive power and the president of the regional committee. Local municipalities are governed by popularly elected municipal councils, municipal committees and the mayor¹⁶. Regions have some control over the activity of the municipalities. At an intermediate administrative level, between the regions and the municipalities, there are the provinces that are organized in a similar manner each having councils, committees, and presidents¹⁷. During emergencies both the president of the regional committee and the mayor of the municipality is charged with central government duties concerning public health emergency management such as response planning and the supervision of the local police forces. Similar to Greece, Italy had a more central, top-down administrative approach, in comparison to Belgium, Austria and Germany.

The main lesson learned at the early stages of COVID 19 outbreak was the fact that even though a National influenza pandemic preparedness and response plan was already in place aiming to strengthen preparedness and response capacities at national and local level, with the advent of the pandemic the pre-existing plans and procedures were ignored allowing thus the virus to circulate freely in Italy¹⁸. Across all levels of administration, local and regional authorities applied specific preventive measures to combat and mitigate the consequences of the pandemic, supported by either pre-existing entities and crisis mechanisms or new bodies such as designated task forces and specialized scientific committees (Armocida et al., 2020).

When a State of Emergency was declared conferring the central government exceptional powers, the overall decision and leadership of the country's efforts were taken under by the Prime's Minister's own responsibility to coordinate the response at all levels of administration¹⁹. Resorting to this emergency legislative tool allowed the main state actors, namely the Civil Protection Department and the Ministry of Health, assisted by a designated Scientific Technical Committee (CTS), to negotiate a minimum action consensus between all different administrative levels (Pistoi, 2021). It was evident at that time that the decentralised administrative structure and the Government's initial response strategy imposed additional challenges inadvertently facilitating the spread of the virus rather than containing it.

¹⁵ D4.1. Baseline report: Governmental responses, p. 30.

¹⁶ Supra note 15.

¹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁸ D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, pp. 142-146.

¹⁹ D4.1 Baseline report: Governmental responses, p. 30.

As the COVID 19 waves evolved, Italy was one of the *COVINFORM* countries that underwent substantial governmental structure changes²⁰. In early 2021, a new government under Mario Draghi was formed coinciding with the end of the first phase of the pandemic. Then, a new government led by Giorgia Meloni, took office as a result of the general elections held in October 2022.

Governmental structure and COVID-19 crisis response system in Portugal

Portugal is a presidential representative democratic republic including two autonomous regions, where the Prime Minister is the head of government. Executive power is exercised by the government which is responsible for the nation's overall policy, including public health emergency management and crisis response²¹. The two aforementioned autonomous regions have respective regional health authorities with administrative autonomy. Portugal abides by a similar administrative approach with Greece and Italy, however, it also incorporates characteristics of fragmented administrations such as observed in Germany, Belgium and Austria, particularly in relation to the regions enjoying enhanced autonomy.

With the advent of the pandemic it was the Portuguese government who assumed the greatest responsibility to lead the response against COVID-19. A main lesson learned prior and during the outbreak of the pandemic (T0) was that the centralized administrative system allowed a State of Alarm to be declared, conferring thus the Government extra powers for swiftly mobilizing and coordinating all levels of administration and relevant state actors and approving extraordinary and urgent measures²² in order to successfully control the spread of the virus.

Another main lesson learned which is identified in Portugal was that in order to manage the situation, the Government had to rely on previously established authorities and governmental structures such as the Directorate-General of Health (DGS) and the National Civil Protection Authority (ANPC) but also on new entities that were created ad hoc such as scientific committees, coordinating groups and designated task forces²³. All these actors worked closely with all governmental departments in order to coordinate more effectively the response to the pandemic. Furthermore, a National Plan for Pandemic Influenza, released in 2007 and revised in 2014, entailing a relevant crisis response framework was also already in place.

It should be noted that although the country underwent election procedures at three different cases²⁴ amidst the pandemic (Presidential and Local Elections on 2021 and Legislative Elections on 2022) the administrative structure did not experience any substantial changes enhancing this way further the Government's effort against COVID-19.

Governmental structure and COVID-19 crisis response system in Spain

The political system in **Spain** is a parliamentary monarchy where the central government plays a leading role in policy making at a national level. The Spanish state is characterised by high

²⁰ D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, pp. 46-49.

²¹ D4.1 Baseline report: Governmental responses, p. 31.

²² Supra note 21.

²³ D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, pp. 49-56.

²⁴ Ibid.

decentralization, similarly to Germany, Austria and Belgium, based upon different levels of government which rule and manage specific areas of public policy having their own administration²⁵. The relevance between the different administrative levels in policymaking is institutionally determined. At the subnational level, Spain is organised into 17 Autonomous Communities and two Autonomous Cities (Ceuta and Melilla) whilst some communities have developed higher levels of decentralisation such as the Basque Country and Navarre which also enjoy a high degree of fiscal autonomy²⁶. Furthermore, the Spanish regions similarly to the national level are parliamentary sub-political systems, whose governments are elected by their own regional parliaments.

At the advent of the pandemic, the Spanish decentralized state model was challenged due to the fact that the autonomous community of Catalonia and Madrid, health system collapsed, which led the Central Government to declare a State of Alarm²⁷. And therefore received [OBJ]. Hence the State of Alarm was put into effect a new coordination structure, the Single Authority was established²⁸[OBJ]. As the pandemic evolved and based on various internal pressures regarding the management of the pandemic and due to the ever-growing needs to coordinate more effectively the implemented policies not only nationwide but especially in the autonomous regions that faced significant health related challenges, the Single Authority was replaced by multiple ²⁹[OBJ] to each regional government with restricted decision-making capacity nonetheless, since the central government kept the competence to intervene whenever deemed necessary.

Considering the de-centralized state model and the highly fragmented administrative system in Spain, a key lesson was to deploy a response strategy nationwide, all state actors had to comply to a minimum consensus regarding the division of powers and responsibilities between central and regional political points of authority. At that end, central government's structures such as the Single Authority played a crucial role in monitoring the evolution of the pandemic and coordinating accordingly the country's response.

Governmental structure and COVID-19 crisis response system in Sweden

The socio-governmental foundation of **Sweden** is based on constitutional monarchy which is supported by the four legal pillars: Freedom of the Press Act, Succession Act, the Parliament (Riksdag) and the Swedish Government, whilst can also be considered a country with a decentralized administration governmental structure. The constitution of Sweden is based on popular sovereignty, representative democracy and parliamentary, therefore, the main governmental systems and actors are the Prime Minister, cabinet members and party leaders, as well as central administrative agencies which reserve autonomous rights in their respective regional and local jurisdiction areas. The administrative management on a regional level is based on 21 countries, administered by regional governors and on a local level, 290 municipalities (kommuner), which are led by elected assemblies.

²⁵ D4.1 Baseline report: Governmental responses, pp. 33.

²⁶ Ibid.

²⁷ Presidencia del Gobierno. (n.d.). *Estado de Alarma*. Retrieved May 26 2021 from

<https://www.lamoncloa.gob.es/covid-19/Paginas/estado-de-alarma.aspx#:~:text=El%20primer%20estado%20de%20alarma,provocada%20por%20el%20COVID%2D19.>

²⁸ D4.1 Baseline report: Governmental responses, pp. 33.

²⁹ Ibid.

The main lesson learned which is identified in **Sweden** prior and during the outbreak of the pandemic (T0), is the de-centralized governance, fragmented administrative system did not experience any adaptations or changes in the governmental structure. This was mainly due to constitutional limitations which do not allow the regulation of emergencies and crises during peacetime, only during periods of war, thus, a curfew or emergency permit could not be imposed. Moreover, based on our expert interviews, during this phase, Sweden was lacking a clear response mechanism and crisis management structure, while experienced several challenges in relation to the integration of all relevant stakeholders in order to construct and conduct an effective COVID-19 response.

The lack of authority in regional and local areas by the central government in Sweden may likely have been a contributing factor which negatively impacted the assembly of an organized, well-structured and prompt crisis management response. This finding is strongly supported by the limitations of policy influence by relevant central government agencies on regional and local communities, who retained their autonomy during this phase. In relation to welfare system and pandemic management in Sweden, all three levels of governance are engaged in the process. To summarise, the decentralised governance system hindered accountability mechanisms and decision making.

Another main lesson is that **Sweden** formulated the national pandemic response on principles that respected the boundaries of governmental and administrative jurisdiction. Sweden did not conduct radical governmental changes that would tip the balance of authority between the three levels of governance but instead, the Swedish crisis response system was based on the principles of responsibility, equality and proximity. Accordingly, actors and systems that were mostly affected and responsible ought to handle societal disturbances, conduct proportional to the case organization changes and continue to carry out activities under normal conditions, taking into consideration the challenges that COVID-19 may present.

Governmental structure and COVID-19 crisis response system in the UK (England & Wales)

The socio-governmental foundation of the **United Kingdom (UK)** consists of England, Wales, Scotland and Northern Ireland. The UK is both a constitutional monarchy and a parliamentary democracy. In the UK parliament, known as the House of Commons, there are members (MP's) representing both England and Wales (UK Parliament, n.d.). The second chamber of the UK Parliament, known as the House of Lords, complements the performance of the House of Commons by making laws, considering in-depth public policy, and holding the government to account. The UK is a unique case, which albeit can be considered to function with a top-down administrative system, the four states have their own unique administrative characteristics, which potentially may present several differences between each other. Regarding emergencies, the planning structure consists of the Civil Contingencies Secretariat (CCS) which is part of the UK Cabinet Office and is in charge for emergency planning and response. The Civil Contingencies Act and accompanying measures provide the framework for civil protection in the entire UK, including the activities that relative entities, such as the Police, National Health System (NHS) and Fire Department must implement in an emergency. At a local level in England and Wales, the aforementioned responders are prepared for emergencies through the Local Resilience Forums (LRFs) (UK Cabinet Office, 2013, February 13). Also, Strategic Coordinating Groups (SCG)s similarly operate at a local level, with documents outlining how it would be likely for the SCGs to be convened in the event of a pandemic to take overall responsibility for the multi-agency management at a local level (UK Cabinet Office, 2013). It should be noted that since 2006, Wales has been given legislative powers, resulting in the creation of a Welsh Parliament and a Welsh Assembly Government,

comprising of a Prime Minister for Wales, Welsh ministers, and deputy ministers. There are twenty areas of responsibility devolved to the National Assembly for Wales, including economic development, health, social welfare, and local governments.

The main lesson learned which is identified in the UK prior and during the outbreak of the pandemic (T0), is the legislated well-structured and decentralized model of administrative system to counter emergencies such the pandemic (Prime Minister's Office, 2020). Which eventually allowed the Prime Minister to issue new ministerial structures to respond to COVID-19 crisis, which included four new implementation committees, focusing on health, public sector preparedness, economy and international response, which in turn participated into the daily COVID-19 meetings led by the Prime Minister himself (UK Cabinet Office, 2020). These committees were ultimately replaced by the 'COVID-19 Strategy' and the 'COVID-19 Operations' cabinet, revealing an evolutionary strategy by the UK in tackling the COVID-19 pandemic.

During the crisis response, the four nations of the UK joined their efforts to respond to the COVID-19 pandemic, with central government also created new ministerial-led taskforces for an efficient re-opening of specific sectors such as restaurants, non-essential stores, tourism etc., (UK Cabinet Office, 2020). However, Wales approved the COVID-19 restrictions by the Welsh Parliament, resulting in independent management of the COVID-19 pandemic, from the other British nations. In Wales, the Public Health department manages the health emergencies, whereas emergency planning might be consistent with the United Kingdom's Civil Contingencies Act 2004, but it also includes the Welsh Government's involvement and the participation of operating organizations that are unique to Wales. Wales Resilience Forum is the highest authority for emergency planning in Wales and works in cooperation with the local resilience forums and other agencies³⁰.

Another lesson learned in the case of the UK, is that the unique unitary state of the country, which is comprised by four nations, can create fragmentations in the drafting of a unified policy towards the COVID-19 pandemic, as seen above with the example of the detachment of Wales from the general management of the taskforces formed by the central government.

3.2 Changes and other developments in Policies and Practice implementation (T1 – T2)

Good practices and main lessons learned from changes in practices and policies in Austria

Austria witnessed no governmental structure changes from the periods of T1 and T2. With regard to the main policy actors to COVID-19 still it remained the federal and province governments, with most responsibilities being embedded in the Ministry of Health (Migration.Gv, n.d.)³¹. The Ministry of Health created the "Corona Taskforce" (Bundesministerium Soziales, Gesundheit, Pflege, und Konsumentenschutz, 2021)³², which is comprised of health and social experts that provide scientific

³⁰ As observed in D.4.1. Baseline report: Governmental responses, p. 36.

³¹ Migration. Gv. (n.d.). The political, administrative and legal systems. Available at: <https://www.migration.gv.at/en/living-and-working-in-austria/austria-at-a-glance/the-political-administrative-and-legal-systems/>.

³² Bundesministerium Soziales, Gesundheit, Pflege, und Konsumentenschutz. (2021, April 19). Coronavirus Taskforce. Available at: [https://www.sozialministerium.at/Informationen-zum-Coronavirus/Neuartiges-Coronavirus-\(2019-nCov\)/Coronavirus---Taskforce.html](https://www.sozialministerium.at/Informationen-zum-Coronavirus/Neuartiges-Coronavirus-(2019-nCov)/Coronavirus---Taskforce.html).

advice on the handling of the crisis. During the second and third wave of the pandemic Austria's responses were influenced by several factors.

The main lesson learned is that the Austrian Government decided to change some of its responses during the second wave and even amend the COVID-19 law, in September 2020, to comply with the Court order (Republic of Austria, 2020)³³, which ruled that some of the restrictive policies taken during March and April 2020 were unconstitutional (Aichinger 2020). For example, the relevant provisions were the general social restrictions as well as the fines issued in connection with the violation of these social restrictions. The Ministry of Health was legally only allowed to issue such restrictions for specific areas instead of imposing general social restrictions. This decision affected the response of the government in the second and third wave. For example, the decision led to an amendment and some clarification of the COVID-19 Policy Act (COVID-19 Maßnahmen Gesetz) in September 2020.

The main **good practices** to address the financial consequences of the pandemic was the Ministry of Finance issuing 41 laws and ordinances. Among them, there was a fund to help small enterprises as well as a regulation mentioning that the state would subsidise employees' wages from companies whose operation was suspended. Another economic measure, which was controversial but important to maintain the country its economic wealth was the decision to keep ski resorts and lifts open during Austria's third lockdown (Vienna Center for Electoral Research, 2021)³⁴. Finally, with regard to the Christian holidays, lockdown restrictions were eased during the holiday season. However, this was not the case for Easter, as the British mutation of the virus and the rising number of cases, led the country to a six-day lockdown in three eastern provinces.

An important social lesson learned which may have influenced the course of the pandemic in Austria was the "low level of intergenerational contact and cohabitation may have helped to isolate elderly vulnerable groups"³⁵.

In Austria, the main **good practice** was that the country implemented a more flexible response to COVID-19 pandemic, as the national government held responsibility to manage it initially, this changed overtime because of different political leadership as well as differing epidemiological developments. So those political areas, where the state government has power over, were more and more decided on a local state level than on the national one. In Austria, with the pandemic ongoing, some segments of society became dissatisfied with the government's pandemic management. Particular issues were ongoing lockdown. Some **good practices** were the fact that Austria implemented some financial responses like COVID-19 Crisis management fund (various funds for different areas), Gesetzliche Budgetprovisorium 2020 (Statutory budget provisional), Arbeitsmarktpolitik-Finanzierungsgesetz (Labor Market Financing Act), short-time work, and support for businesses.

Good practices and main lessons learned from changes in practices and policies in Belgium

³³ Republic of Austria. (2020, September 25). Änderung des Epidemiegesetzes 1950, des Tuberkulosegesetzes und des COVID-19-Maßnahmengesetzes (NR: GP XXVII IA 826/A AB 370 S. 51. BR: AB 10408 S. 912.). Available at: https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/BgblAuth/BGBLA_2020_I_104/BGBLA_2020_I_104.pdf#sig.

³⁴ Vienna Center for Electoral Research. (2021, February 19). Chronology of the Corona crisis in Austria - Part 4: Renewed lockdowns, mass tests and the start of the vaccination campaign – Corona blog 100. Available at: <https://viecer.univie.ac.at/corona-blog/corona-blog-beitrag/blog100/>.

³⁵ Ibid.

The response of the government of **Belgium** was shaped based on legal factors. Measures affecting fundamental rights have been implemented through a ministerial decision under the Political Security Act of 2007, which was designed for acute emergencies but not for long-term health crises (Verbergt, 2020b). The caretaker government in Belgium had been given special powers to address the effects of the pandemic (Rankin, 2020).

Until October 2020 the “consultation structure” that consisted of pre-existing and newly created bodies was responsible for reporting to the National Security Council and Commission (Desson et al. 2020)³⁶. In particular, the newly created bodies were responsible for:

- a. *The Risk Assessment Group (pre), which analyses risk, based on scientific epidemiological data*
- b. *The Risk Management Group (pre), charged with deciding what are the appropriate measures against COVID-19, after receiving advice from RAG.*
- c. *The Economic Risk Management Group (March 2020) responsible for financial matters*
- d. *The Expert Strategy Exit Group (April 2020).*

After October 2020, with the election of the new Government, a new advisory committee has been set up to decide on all relevant COVID-19 responses.

The Minister for Security and Foreign Affairs was then responsible for issuing ministerial decrees and their application is described in the following section from the National Crisis Center. Further regulations are also implemented by the local governments in their respective regions on issues relating to education, elderly care and health services (Reybrouck, 2020)³⁷. Furthermore, to fight the pandemic control of the contamination rate the Flemish Department Health and Family Affairs developed their own protocols (Departement Welzijn, Volksgezondheid en Gezin, n.d.)³⁸.

However, the main lesson learned is that this overlapping of responsibilities has led to the designation of Belgian responses as confusing and inefficient mainly because of bureaucratic delays in decision-making and litigation concerning jurisdiction (Merckx S. and Delespaul A., 2020)³⁹.

During the T1 phase, the initial response in Belgium involved the necessary lockdowns, measures and approval of the Crown barometer, which supported the preparation and communication of the policy. A characteristic element of the barometer was that it consisted of three phases: yellow, orange and

³⁶ De Standaard. (2020, April 6). Tien experts moeten België uit lockdown leiden. Retrieved June 27, 2023, from https://www.standaard.be/cnt/dmf20200406_04914854.

³⁷ Karel Reybrouck (2020, November 13) Hoe het Coronavirus onze bevoegdheidsverdeling op de proef stelt. Available at: https://www.leuvenpubliclaw.com/hoe-het-coronavirus-onze-%20bevoegdheidsverdeling-op-de-proef%20stelt/?_cf_chl_captcha_tk_=6e912a6aa9c7b0637274440695b32c57363504b8-1622130194-0-AR5cpeMwD5gh0bllqQYS1RjqaIdB_9KCsgCHIc69PX3zDGD7qTYftoF5NjHLc4AiltNlrwJ_qZ9TG27v-2t3-%20V0zfKDTcgh8nUjn0JJGDF4AjdG2CP1QtKFqG-%20SKDkPpRkP5IexgGONf9yoZfbens2n8c21yTWUAKNwqE7Zl1M3iLjby04rh-%201U6Mm1sl3g6oa15Bjy384MMIJCFE2KXly37Jbmzc0iuF4LjO-%20L0c1SyhKN3K4kz5nt8LZfLqLxBakvb35lPh1DQKmj127V-%20xHZQISigYMFqGLyrrN6L3RB3jUaG9dt0SZterWkfbzEgQvkhJw0BDCNif8778Dk7EQGtJoHMqsjbBiMBQcDj9SVx68g%208f14a-I0CMVds6wiXZNhq0vTnUc-%20YkZsiT6P5sm1Wreb7NJo9kE8PQrnYwJDBnhKTIFZiHefcxViFJhTgto9mTCZzjFk88tdF5VcWeXBXOKhyhd8g_Hwa%20a2WhFvUd_gCJyc58-B5yIEmiqSawCdX0o-sH8-jlpzZylgmaV3cahw21xwyFpz9Nn6Mh9WauUveNsVXrbu-%20Y8YSCT4cAlchLUnh19cUcUAscB_bDOO_QKgs51sPxaWm3u9a8KRj2cVdFp48Xy6uCZLgXbFXPisF5bcJ9akeKv7_1_P%20C2Gw5Z4WgLH4DIOf6WSe69LK_2dljxQe0LeRhxQ_uAmntNxUhWZUx3-%207Rz6VeevGuxNCmSgFBPQn9Kj4DJCJ44FDlvpkt0MEcdJCS82hOimIA.

³⁸ Departement Welzijn, Volksgezondheid en Gezin. (n.d). Over het departement. Available at: <https://www.departementwvg.be/over-het-departement>.

³⁹ Merckx S. and Delespaul A. (2020, June 19). Waarom we nood hebben aan één federale minister van gezondheid. Solidair. Available at: <https://www.solidair.org/artikels/longread-waarom-we-nood-hebben-aan-een-federale-minister-van-gezondheid>.

red. During the T2 phase, the change in response was that the COVID-19 measures were progressively loosened and removed.

In Belgium, the complexity of the governance system was criticized. Cooperation between institutions/representatives was good in situations where responsibilities were clear and where they had similar responsibilities and interests. However, when various people had to work together and had very different responsibilities, this complex decision-making process.

In addition, tensions in coordination between federal and regional decision-making levels have been highlighted, as economic reasons have often been given. Criticism was also voiced as Belgium's COVID-19 policy was seen as reactionary and short-term, with no transparency and long-term planning.

According to our expert interviews, links with communities were seen as important. A lesson learned could thus be to strengthen communities more through trustworthy personalities, as well as to deepen community organizations and declare their presence. In addition, a lesson learned is to provide information in a good and appropriate way, through people who have credibility in the streets and are trustworthy to those involved.

Finally, a **good practice** was that the government did well by focusing more on efforts to locate contacts. The 'federal phase' of governance of the COVID-19 pandemic in Belgium was completed in March 2022 with the result that regional authorities, governors and local administrations are now legally responsible again for managing the pandemic (National Crisis Centrum, 2022).

The Belgian Government has taken a balancing act between the protection of public health and the protection of economic interests. Although the Belgian economy has shown significant reductions in turnover in various sectors, signs of recovery have emerged, such as relatively low job losses and positive trends in the employment situation (FOD Economie, 2022).

Good practices and main lessons learned from changes in practices and policies in Germany

In **Germany**, a federal parliamentary election was held on 26 September 2021, which led to a change in government. After two months of talks, the SPD (Social Democratic Party), Greens, and FDP (Free Democratic Party) formed a novel coalition government on 23 November 2021. Olaf Scholz of the SPD was selected as Chancellor on 8 December 2021 (Nienaber, 2021)⁴⁰.

Regarding government changes in Germany the initial response to the COVID-19 pandemic was the rollout of hygiene regulations developed by the Robert Koch Institute. These hygiene regulations included compulsory mask-wearing in public, as well as the definition of a risk communication strategy based on the slogan „through the year with AHA (mit AHA durchs Jahr)“. These crisis mitigation measures were:

- 1) „Abstandhalten“ – “keep a safe distance”.
- 2) „Hygiene-Maßnahmenbeachten“ – “pay attention to hygiene measures”.
- 3) „Alltagsmasketragen“ – “wear a mask on an everyday basis” (Federal Center for Health Education, n.d.)⁴¹.

The implementation of lockdowns during this time period depended on the severity of infection and death case rates. Social distancing measures remained in place, while during summer 2020, restrictive measures were adopted flexibly on a state-by-state level in response to local infection rates. On a

⁴⁰ Nienaber, M. (2021). Scholz takes over as German chancellor, ending merkel era. Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/world/europe/social-democrat-olaf-scholz-elected-german-chancellor-2021-12-08/>.

⁴¹ Federal Center for Health Education (BZgA). (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.infektionsschutz.de/coronavirus/alltag-in-zeiten-von-corona/>.

federal level, the first hard lockdown was phased out on 19 April 2020. In October 2020, when both case rates and deaths began to increase, the federal government implemented a second hard lockdown on 2 November, which extended until 19 December.

During the period of T2 in Germany, infection rates and to a lesser extent, death rates – continued well into 2022. In April 2022 many of the remaining restrictive measures, such as the requirement to wear masks in shops, were lifted. That said, masks in hospitals and on public transportation were mandatory. A wave of increased infection and death rates in June 2022 did not substantially affect federal policy, that means that some new rules were implemented on a state-by-state level but most were minor. By Winter 2022, the consensus among public-facing experts was that COVID-19 had evolved into an endemic (rather than pandemic) disease (ibid).

The main lesson is that the communication during the T1 period was incomplete, which led many times to confusion not only for the general public, but also for local managers and frontline workers, and that efforts were made to introduce greater clarity by adapting higher-level communications locally.

More specifically, throughout this period, the federal government and the state government were often criticized for inconsistency in issuing and notifying new restrictions. As According to our expert interviews: *"Federal and state policy over and over again also contributed to the fact that the decrees sometimes came in a very short time and that the commandments for communication took place in a language that was not understood by many. I do not exclude myself at all points [...] We have tried to find ways at the municipal level, but maybe we will come to this later."*

According to the evaluation report of the committee of experts of the ministry of health, a **good practice** is that the communication strategy is alternated and adapted in various ways, thus becoming more targeted and effective, as the pandemic progressed whereas data and expert knowledge were acquired (BMG 2022: 50).

In conclusion, governmental risk communication in the first phase of the pandemic was linear and direct, a strategy justified by lack of data and knowledge. As the pandemic progressed, however, studies became accessible to the public, opinions started to vary and decisions were made based on scientific evidence. Communication, on the other hand, did not progress and adapt but instead remained top-down, failed to target essential population groups and did not allow for a democratic dialogue.

A second lesson is that in the years 2021 and 2022, the German Government addressed the issue of vaccination against COVID-19 and in particular the decision-makers in Germany were criticized for their Communication on vaccination (BMG 2022:57). In Germany, ad hoc decisions were based on the 7-day incidence rate of COVID-19. The German Government did not publicly identify any other factors or indicators on which these decisions are based. Some controversial measures introduced under the COVID-19 Protective Measures Exemption Decree (COVID-19-Schutzma Bonnahmen-Ausnahmenverordnung) and implemented mainly at State level and not at federal level were as follows: In the first and second quarters of 2021, the "2G/2G+/3G" Regulations were implemented, meaning that only vaccinated, recovered and/or tested persons could have access to restaurants, events or other services.

However, based on official assessments and studies, we can form an insight into the factors that may have affected and/or limited the government's preparedness and response. According to a study by the University of Erfurt, the public in the initial phase of the pandemic expressed relatively high confidence in public health institutions and public administration, accompanied by relatively high acceptance of the measures taken (Universität Erfurt et al., 2022).

The 2001 Infektionsschutzgesetz (IfSG) was evaluated by BMG as "designed entirely for outbreaks of a rather local nature and of limited duration". In conclusion, it was difficult to base almost all measures covering the entire population and the whole country to combat the long-term Corona pandemic on

this law. The practitioners tried to complete this work mainly through numerous, not always random, amendments and additions to the IfSG, with little evidence of a coherent overall approach. Instead, IfSG has developed into a rather confused and non-systematic network of regulations (BMG 2022, p. m) 103). This restriction led to considerable confusion in terms of the notification of the amended measures and the rationale behind them, which ultimately led to a decrease in public acceptance.

Finally, the 2017 National Pandemic Plan undertakes the moral obligation to protect the medically vulnerable population groups as a key element in managing a pandemic. Therefore, the general population was expected to sacrifice certain rights and freedoms in order to allow the authorities to fulfill this obligation.

Changes and other developments in Policies and Practice implementation in Greece

Greece was among the EU countries that declared the State of Emergency/Alert for managing the pandemic (in the case of Greece a State of Alert). These countries resorted to emergency legislative tools, foreseen in their constitutional and institutional design for periods of emergency, alarm or crisis. Depending on each country, exceptional powers are given to national governments to respond to critical events (from natural disasters to political, economic or social crises), such as the pandemic (Stefan and Chun Luk, 2021). Depending on each country's constitution and related legal framework, the State of Emergency/Alert allowed governments to assume decisions that they would be unable to make in normal circumstances. Under this new exceptional regime, countries were able to restrict the freedom of movement, air traffic, requisitions of some goods, and other measures such as countrywide curfews, cancellations of large events, or mandatory quarantines for travelers entering the country, actions that Greece took during most of the pandemic period⁴².

According to the majority of interviewees involved with the government policies to tackle the pandemic and their implementation, the additional workload, tasks and responsibility in response to the COVID-19, needed to be adapted and tailored to manage the disease in an efficient way. The introduction of several legislative acts by the central government, allowed preparation and management of the pandemic, since measures and regulations could now be legally implemented. Most of the interviewees, mentioned that the response and management in Greece, was comparable with the majority of responses in EU countries and adhered to the WHO international standards. Various policies increased the containment, control, and management of the pandemic, although their intensity was declining over time. There is an overall satisfaction with the efficiency of the pandemic management, with the relevant legislative acts, as well as additional initiatives for the distribution of responsibilities within the government structures, for the increased response effectiveness of the measures in Greece. Although research showed that communication between government agencies and the public presented gaps, there is general satisfaction with the coordination between agencies and organizations with the central roles in pandemic management. For that reason and due to the nature of the crisis, health experts were heavily involved in pandemic planning and responses. The country had a lockdown and was expected that this plan would always depending on the evolution of the disease, with the government reviewing each measure every 24 hours in case they needed to be corrected, and with citizens being required to carry a QR code, explaining why they were leaving their homes. Also, in Greece it was compulsory at work and services, as well as in transport, to wear facemasks⁴³.

⁴² As observed in D4.1 Baseline report: Governmental responses, pp. 23-36 and D.4.3 Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment, pp. 22-26.

⁴³ As observed in D4.3 Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment, p. 47.

The main lesson learned identified in Greece, particularly during the start of the pandemic, up to the vaccination campaign (but also from the vaccination until now (T1)), is the fast introduction and adaptation of legislation by the central government. In a stepwise manner, addressed most of the consequences of COVID-19, generally managing effectively the unprecedented situation, but without much authority transferred in regional and local areas. Also, it is observed that Greece followed the general trend in the EU, that of declaring a State of Emergency/Alert, which according to governments, appeared to help towards the containing of the COVID-19, in the early period, when little was known about the disease.

Good practices and main lessons learned from changes in practices and policies in Italy

Since the outbreak of COVID 19 and as the pandemic evolved strict non-pharmacological preventive measures were adopted throughout **Italy**⁴⁴. These measures aiming to control the further spread of the virus included total or partial lockdowns, physical distancing and compulsory mask wearing in indoor environments, such as means of transport and crowded public places, countrywide curfews, restrictions to people's inter-municipal mobility, suspension of economic activity, suspension of face – to face teaching activities at all levels of education and cancellations of cultural, athletic or other social events⁴⁵. In addition to that, strict prohibitions were also imposed in terms of national borders closure, air traffic control and mandatory quarantines for travellers entering the country⁴⁶.

The division of the Italian territory by four different colour zones, in which each colour symbolised the severity of infections in a specific area, and were based on the evaluation of several epidemiological and health system indicators. Different measures applied depending on the respective zone of each region, in combination with the response capacities provided by the declared State of Emergency that was put in effect, were acknowledged as **good practices** and were extended in the long term⁴⁷. In the context of a positively evolving health situation illustrated by the slowdown of the COVID 19 infection curve mainly because the acceleration of the vaccination programme, a recovery strategy based on three pillars was introduced in Italy⁴⁸. The de-escalation strategy included an explicit road map of economic activities re-opening, measures to support further the economy and businesses and measures for the revival of the economic growth. From that time and onwards the restrictive measures were gradually revoked up until April 2022 where the Italian Government declared the end of the “coloured” zone system and the definitive cessation of the State of Emergency lifting all relevant restrictions⁴⁹.

During the timeframe under study (T1-T2), the Government acknowledged that the pandemic, except the significant negative consequences it had on people's health, also had a huge socio-economic impact on the whole population⁵⁰. To this end, additional measures were announced to mitigate the economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and minimize the economic recession which emphasized on compensating employees and businesses that were affected by the suspension of employment and

⁴⁴ D4.5. Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, p. 106, 142-146.

⁴⁵ Ibid.

⁴⁶ D4.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts, pp. 13-32.

⁴⁷ D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, pp. 46-49, 142-146.

⁴⁸ Ibid.

⁴⁹ Ibid.

⁵⁰ D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, pp. 142-146.

economic activity and on supporting individuals and families who suffered a significant drop in income⁵¹.

Substantial anti-poverty funds were allocated to support families and workers in need regarding the payment of rents and household utilities, while emergency food solidarity programmes were also deployed (Gazzetta Ufficiale, 2021). The applied measures also strengthened aid for businesses affected by the crisis, covering fixed costs, such as rents and utility bills, as well as interventions to foster credit and liquidity and tax deferrals and exemptions. There were also extra resources allocated to especially support young people and local authorities as well, through the launch of numerous public works, non-refundable investments and loans⁵².

Good practices and main lessons learned from changes in practices and policies in Portugal

As the pandemic evolved, a main lesson learned was the government realising that its main priorities should focus not only on combating and controlling COVID 19 but also on mitigating the economic impacts of the pandemic.⁵³ In addition, it was recognised that particular attention should be paid to the recovery of the **Portuguese** economy, protecting household income, employment and business activity.

The deployment of a programmed and targeted testing strategy was identified as a successful practice in detecting early, rapidly and effectively new COVID 19 cases and thus in containing the further spread of the virus. In this context, the early strict measures applied during the first phases of the pandemic in order to minimize social interaction and personal contacts such as home confinement, suspension of specific economic and social activities including suspension of face-to-face teaching and compulsory facemasks wearing in public spaces, underwent substantial adaptations depending on the prevailing epidemiological situation across the country and the subsequent pressure put on hospitals and the health system⁵⁴. As the national crisis response evolved so to adapt to changing circumstances and challenges, the State of Alarm was gradually lifted and replaced by a State of Calamity that entailed more relax restrictions⁵⁵. National lockdowns, border closures and travelling restrictions were substituted by other policies such as curfews, partial restriction of citizens' inter-municipality circulation, implementation of telework whenever possible and permission of travelling between countries under specific requirements (meaning the EU digital COVID Certificate or recent negative PCR or antigen tests).

Given the fact that the vaccination against COVID-19 gradually reached adequate uptake in the population, another **good practice** in Portugal was the introduction of a clear de-confinement plan⁵⁶ that entailed the de-escalation of the restriction measures. The plan was divided into four distinct phases, with a period of 15 days between each one in order to assess the impact the implemented measures had on the evolution of the pandemic⁵⁷.

⁵¹ Ibid.

⁵² Ibid.

⁵³ D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, pp. 49-56.

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ Resolução do Conselho de Ministros n.º 64-A/2021, 2021-05-28

<https://eportugal.gov.pt/pt/noticias/governo-anuncia-plano-de-desconfinamento-ate-3-de-maio>.

⁵⁷ D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, pp. 146-152.

Nonetheless, the emergence of the Omicron variant in late 2021 which led to a significant resurgence of COVID-19 cases in the country, forced the government and health authorities to reintroduce specific measures, such as mask mandates and capacity restrictions for social activities in public spaces⁵⁸.

Significant efforts were also made in an attempt to compensate the negative socioeconomic impacts of the pandemic by implementing enhanced economic measures, such as long-term and short-term programs and financial support to both employees and businesses⁵⁹, aiming at economic recovery and return to normal business continuity and operation as soon as possible. In addition to that as the country heavily relies on tourism, emphasized economic support was significantly directed at the relative industry⁶⁰, ensuring nonetheless that standing tourist restrictions were respected at all times.

Good practices and main lessons learned from changes in practices and policies in Spain

When the pandemic hit **Spain**, the initial response included the declaration of the State of Alarm and the implementation of lockdowns that allowed only the most essential activities such as visits to supermarkets, pharmacies and health care services⁶¹. People were obliged to home confinement and only those who were employed to essential services and supplies were allowed to go out. Once the early stage of the pandemic was overcome, and the epidemiological situation in the country was improved mainly because of the thorough expansion of the population's vaccine uptake, a gradual return to normality was introduced and the imposed lockdown was substituted by other policies such as curfews and inter-territory control of movement⁶².

Since April 2021, the Spanish state directed all efforts to restore the pre-pandemic context in the country not only regarding government structures, response mechanisms and designated authorities but also in relation to the restrictions imposed to enforce social distance and the deployment of economic measures to support those who were economically hit by the pandemic. The emergency state used to diminish the spreading of the Covid-19 in Spain, the State of Alarm, which conferred special powers to both the central and the regional governments was revoked in May 2021⁶³.

From that time onwards, there was no need neither to approve any other State of Alarm or any exceptional or emergency regulations even when the Omicron variant emerged.⁶⁴ The main restrictions affecting citizens' fundamental rights, such as the freedom of movement (lockdowns, curfews, or limits to move from one territory to another), were considered from that time onwards unnecessary. Regular legislation was enough to keep, approve and enforce any applied limitations which mainly had to do with the compulsory use of masks in specific locations such as means of transportation and crowded public spaces, some restrictions to reinforce social distance and the COVID 19 Vaccination Passport necessary to attend events or hostelry services in some regions⁶⁵.

Since it was evident that all applied measures and restrictions heavily impacted social and economic life in Spain, as soon as mobility restrictions were abrogated, all efforts were consecrated to restore

⁵⁸ Ibid.

⁵⁹ D4.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts, pp. 13-32.

⁶⁰ Ibid.

⁶¹ D4.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts, pp. 13-32.

⁶² D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, pp. 56-58, 151-153.

⁶³ Ibid.

⁶⁴ Ibid.

⁶⁵ Ibid.

the growth of the economy and enhance the recovery of the country to pre-pandemic levels. Several fiscal instruments were designed and introduced to protect citizens of unemployment due to the suspension of economic activity such as the ERTES programme which entailed wage replacements and other benefits when economic activity was suspended⁶⁶. In addition to that both national and regional governments focused on applying and designing policies to implement the European Recovery Fund - Next Generation while Spain received the first part of the funds and the national budget has been approved to modernize and make more competitive the Spanish Economy.

Good practices and main lessons learned from changes in practices and policies in Sweden

Good practices during T1 upon examination of this phase include the implementation of a legal framework that allow governmental decision making entities to implement necessary measures to effectively contain the infection rate and mitigate subsequent negative socio-economic, psychological and cultural impacts. The Swedish response mechanism during T1 conducted several interventions within the **Swedish** community such as: restaurant closure and alcohol sale restriction (Restaurant Act (Act 2020: 526) and Ordinance (2020: 956), the implementation of economic measures and a legislative framework (COVID-19 Act), providing the government with decision-making authority capacity to issue binding pandemic containment measures. Swedish health authorities conducted dissemination activities on the main governmental site Krisinfromation.se which communicated information on multiple languages in easy-to-read format.

The main lesson learned is that there is an imperative need to conduct accurate responses by implementing tailored measures and policies in accordance with the infection rates during health crises. These regulate commercial centres, private and public gatherings events and public transportation while economic, psychological, social and cultural considerations should be taken into account during the policy making process.

Moreover, a crisis organization was implemented by the Public Health Authority (PHA) and activated pandemic plans, similarly to other countries, which were developed after the Influenza-Swine flu case of 2011, which functioned as a base and were tailored for the COVID-19 response. Another **good practice** on a governmental level is that utilising preparedness plans and taking lessons from previous crises, can assist decision makers with the implementation of a more effective response towards contemporary health crises and threats. In comparison to other countries, Swedish responses were less strict, particularly to legislation weaknesses and analyses produced by different expert agencies such as NBHW and PHA. At the early phases of the pandemic, Sweden decided to keep borders and educational facilities open, and despite criticism, the general public supported and approved this approach. At the same time, Sweden limited visitations of care homes, public gatherings and remote teaching was encouraged. The main lesson in this case is that if several expert bodies of equal importance produced estimations that may influence decision making, it could increase governmental response indecisiveness. Decision makers, considered expert opinion of multi-polarity beneficial. This may have influenced the speed of the decision-making process and resulted in unsuitable measures being implemented, due to seeing agreement on differentiated expert views. This approach could also have considered the political cost that stricter measures could introduce.

⁶⁶ D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, pp. 151-153.

Overall, the Swedish pandemic management structure was similar to the rest of the target countries. Main decision making bodies cooperated with the scientific community, while the PHA had a central role and issued recommendations for municipalities and regions in accordance with scientific evidence. The chief epidemiologist Anders Tegnell, had a central role for communication activities and presented key analyses and recommendations issued by the PHA, in daily press conferences. A **good practice** that can be identified is that crises require a multi-dimensional approach. The contribution of the scientific and academic community is highly important to the decision making process. Another main lesson learned that can be identified is that the response of each crisis should be tailored in accordance with the characteristics of relevant risks and threats, whereas decision making should be supported by scientific evidence while communication activities such as press conferences should be assigned to relevant, reputable experts who are highly trusted by the general public.

During this phase the PHA was held accountable for rising fatality rates in care facilities while appointed experts were engaged in regional and local governance levels on administrative issues. The national crisis management was however considered as ineffective, while collaboration between local and regional levels was interpreted functional on problem solving. The main lesson learned was the counterproductive relationship of the fragmented governmental structure between the national government and government agencies on a local and regional level who were assigned with crisis management tasks without prior experience. Another point of criticism was the collection of data without feedback on how it was used. Due to these considerations, a fragmented crisis management response is identified as non-efficient in comparison to a central-government approach.

During the second wave, the Swedish response was fortified as PHA actively encouraged the use of facemasks in public transportation, while Sweden on January 10, 2021 implemented the temporary Act, a legislation allowing the government to adopt more binding communicable disease control measures. In addition, on February 2021 Sweden implemented travel restrictions on EU/EES and Nordic countries and encouraged self-isolation. Travellers would now be required a negative test to enter the country, a measure in place since 2020 for non-EU travellers. As of June 30th, 2021, this measure was replaced by the EU vaccine certificate.

Public gathering restriction measures were lifted during the summer of 2021, increasing the capacity of audiences during events, while keeping distance at restaurants was also waived. Despite the relaxation of measures, the Pandemic Act would be prolonged. At this phase (late T1 – early T2), vaccines were made available, hence the vaccination program would officially be rolled out, therefore at the end of September 2021, 78% of the Swedish population would receive one dose while 69% two doses.

On December 8, 2021 Magdalena Andersson⁶⁷ would succeed Stefan Löfven. The new prime minister declared a new plan to contain the virus. Step 1 highlighted social distancing, Step 2 underlined the importance of vaccine certificates which were mandatory for public gatherings and Step 3 regulated the opening hours of businesses and number of visitors. Changes also occurred to the crisis management structure, while responsibility was moved closer to the Cabinet office (Statsrådsberedningen). During this phase, the General director of PHA was replaced by Karin Tegmark

⁶⁷ Stefan Löfven resigned from office and Magdalena Andersson became the first female Swedish Prime Minister. Both are Social Democratic politicians and the resignation of Stefan Löfven was not related to the pandemic, but to the general election 2022 where he would not candidate for a new term of office.

Wisell. In December 2021, stricter measures were introduced including mandatory vaccination certificates for travellers (Regeringen.se, 2021)⁶⁸, gathering in public places and events were once again limited⁶⁹, while as of the new year due to the spread of the Omicron variant, infection rates were particularly high⁷⁰. Most restrictions would be lifted once again as of February 2022, particularly in relation to the transportation and business – event attendee capacity, as well as the end of remote working and teaching (Clason, 2022)⁷¹. As of April 1st, 2022, COVID-19 was removed from the socially dangerous disease classification, which was no longer subjected to the Infection Protection Act, which subsequently caused the Pandemic Act to be lifted (Regeringskansliet, 2023)⁷².

The main lesson learned during this phase highlights the importance of decision making and policy implementation assessment process during crises. Decision makers and policy experts are highly **recommended** to thoroughly examine the subsequent impact and effectiveness rates of each policy and practice that relates to a crisis, identify weaknesses and conduct alterations by tailoring responses in order to address more effectively a current crisis situation. This process should be conducted frequently with extreme scrutiny, without taking into consideration the political cost and prioritising the good health of both general public and vulnerable groups.

Changes and other developments in Policies and Practice implementation in the UK (England & Wales)

The **UK** was among the countries of the European continent that introduced emergency legislation. The Civil Contingencies Act 2004 allows for the making of temporary special legislation (emergency regulations) to assist in handling with severe emergencies. In addition, the use of these legislative powers would not however prevent the Government from facing legal challenges against any policies implemented using these powers. (Stefan and Chun Luk, 2021). Depending on each country's constitution and related legal framework, the State of Emergency/Alert allowed their governments to assume decisions that they would be otherwise unable to make in normal circumstances. Under this new exceptional regime, the European countries were able to restrict the freedom of movement, air traffic, requisitions of some goods, and other measures such as countrywide curfews, cancellations of large events, or mandatory quarantines for travelers entering the country, some actions that the UK eventually took during in various stages of the pandemic period, although reluctant to impose containment measures at the start of the COVID-19 crisis, finally imposed lockdown procedures⁷³.

The main lesson learned identified with the UK, is that there were unaligned responses to the pandemic in England and Wales, which were very different and not always coordinated, because they had the responsibility and powers to introduce specific health-related measures on their own. Interviewees from Wales mentioned that since the COVID-19 pandemic started, collaborations

⁶⁸ <https://www.regeringen.se/pressmeddelanden/2021/12/andringar-i-inreseforbuden-till-sverige/>.

⁶⁹ <https://www.msn.com/sv-se/nyheter/international/d%3%a4rf%3%b6r-g%3%a4ller-restriktioner-%3%a4ven-vaccinerade-%e2%80%9domikron%e2%80%9d/vi-AAS1Cee>.

⁷⁰ Ibid.

⁷¹ <https://www.expressen.se/nyheter/coronaviruset/sverige-danmark-norge-darfor-oppnar-vi-upp-igen/>.

⁷² <https://www.regeringen.se/pressmeddelanden/2022/03/tillfalliga-smittskyddslogar-slutar-galla-den-31-mars/>.

⁷³ As observed in D.4.1. Baseline report: Governmental responses, pp. 23-36.

between agencies and stakeholders improved considerably, but agreed that many policies were introduced on the UK-wide level, which made them difficult to apply in Wales. As a result, there was often a lot of confusion, whether new pandemic-related strategies could apply to the entire UK or just to Wales. The multiple changes in actions, announced by the many different actors of the central government within a short period of time, increased uncertainty and made it difficult for Wales-based inhabitants to comply with the new rules. Also, the central government was committed to a strategy of herd immunity, thus was reluctant to impose containment measures at the start of the pandemic, however, a lockdown was eventually imposed. Along the pandemic period, the national authorities realized that it was more effective to provide local governments, with the necessary funds to implement and manage the measures taken to mitigate the effects of the COVID-19 crisis⁷⁴.

Interviewees from England, mentioned that the initial focus of the pandemic response was mostly related to public health issues, continuing public administration mechanisms, and providing essential services. However, with the continuing spread of the virus and the large infection of people without the need for hospitalization, the significance of social care became more evident, and therefore measures had to be taken to address the social consequences of the pandemic. Thus, there was a shift to particular management on a local level, guided by central objectives⁷⁵.

The main lesson learned here, according to interviewees, is that the partnerships between (local) organizations became strengthened during the pandemic, resulting in much closer community engagement and communication, with them agreeing that it is important to keep those relationships intact also in a post-pandemic crisis scenario⁷⁶.

3.3 Vulnerability during COVID-19 and the governmental crisis management (T0 – T1 – T2)

The interpretation of vulnerability and governmental responses in Austria

The **Austrian** government's decision-makers chose to focus around "risk groups" rather than touching on "vulnerability". So the Ministry of Health identified those groups with the help of certain variables and more specifically health-related indicators such as chronic diseases, cancer, obesity, diabetes, and other health conditions.

In order to protect the citizens of these groups, a number of measures were taken, such as the Social Security Act (Sozialversicherungsgesetz, 2020)⁷⁷, which gave health risk groups the possibility of working from home, paid leave and protective equipment (all of these were not necessarily adopted by employers). Finally, the unemployed were eligible for increased social support (Desson et al. 2020). The main lesson learned as can be seen from the above examples is the fact that although Austria took measures for people at risk because of health or social difficulties, it neglected to consider "other dimensions such as race, nationality, sexuality, legal status..."⁷⁸ (ibid.).

In Austria, the government included among the vulnerable groups those at higher risk of experiencing severe symptoms and in whom the disease could potentially be life-threatening, such as people over the age of 65, as well as people with (chronic) pre-existing conditions of all ages.

⁷⁴ As observed in D 4.3 Analysis: Government responses to COVID-19 and impact assessment, pp. 55-58.

⁷⁵ Supra note 74.

⁷⁶ Ibid.

⁷⁷ Austrian Federal Law Official Gazzette. (2020, December 31). General Social Insurance Act - COVID-19 risk certificate. Available at:

<https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/Dokumente/Bundesnormen/NOR40223704/NOR40223704.html>.

⁷⁸ Ibid.

One of the **good practices** was the recognition of negative secondary effects such as loneliness created through school closures, through lockdowns and social distancing measures. A **good practice** was measures to support children, since the education ministry referred to the extent of school closures, deciding that restrictions will be reduced to the absolute minimum and will be in accordance with regulations in other areas of life.

Finally, in Austria, it was generally recognized that exclusion and social distancing measures contributed to loneliness.

Good practices for financial support for vulnerable groups included the protection of high-risk groups, which was regulated through the Social Security Act (Sozialversicherungsgesetz). The measures taken included the home office, paid leave, protective equipment, and so forth. **Good practices** for financial support for vulnerable groups included the protection of high-risk groups, which was regulated through the Social Security Act (Sozialversicherungsgesetz). The measures taken related to the home office, paid leave, protective equipment, financial support for workers and employers including small businesses and companies. A typical example is the Short Work Program, where employers take workers off their payroll and subsidize their salaries from the government, the Financial Difficulties Fund (Härtefallfond) for small businesses and one-person companies, a Corona Fund and a Fixed Costs Grant Program (IHS 2020 May, Desson 2020). The Härtefallfond expired in May 2022 and the Fixed Costs Grant Program already expired in August 2021.

The interpretation of vulnerability and governmental responses in Belgium

In **Belgium**, there were concerns about the way certain social groups were treated and approached, as there was a lot of unknown information about how this was done. Segregated data, such as data by migration background, will provide more information on how some groups are disproportionately affected, but there are fears that such data collection could lead to further stigmatization and discrimination.

Another lesson learned, based on our expert interviews, is that there was no data infrastructure to provide sufficient data to specific groups to start planning actions and interventions to raise awareness. There were concerns about communication and, in particular, limited resources and capacities to carry out tailored approaches for the population.

In addition, another lesson we could learn is that at the height of the fourth COVID-19 wave, there were cases that citizens within the general population, were no longer invited for contact tracing. Instead, text messages were sent. This of course leads to a faceless communication and much lower quality than for example a careful phone conversation or a face to face contact. The main lesson learned in Belgium is that distancing measures have had an impact on the emotional sector and particularly increased feelings of loneliness. Moreover, the loss of the social aspect of education due to the closure of schools has had a great impact on the mental well-being of children and young people. The contribution of several local initiatives from communities was necessary to adequately inform and in some cases persuade people that lived in extremely diverse neighbourhoods regarding COVID-19 vaccinations (Geldof et al., 2022).

The main lesson learned was that communication with vulnerable groups could take place at community level through social services, other local government services and local non-profit organizations (Crisiscentrum, 2020)⁷⁹. Also, an important contribution was made to updating the official page of the Belgian Government, which provided multilingual information on vaccination, brochures and audio brochures. On the Service for Integration and Social Integration's website, information about the vaccination campaign is available in different languages (including Dutch), and formats. The site also features a page with important lessons and tools for reaching vulnerable groups

⁷⁹ For example, the Institute of Tropical Medicine in Antwerpen conducted information sessions on the vaccination with community based organisations working with vulnerable groups.

with a migrant background, with examples and best practices from various Flemish cities and municipalities. They also launched the Crisis Information Translate (CIT) mobile application for free, providing non-native speakers with up-to-date and accurate information about vaccination and current coronation measures in 18 languages. This includes the route of administration of the vaccination center and the medical questionnaire.

Finally, a **good practice** is that several municipalities such as Antwerp, Genk, Ghent and Brussels have also provided information on vaccinations for poorly educated and non-native speakers on their local websites and on the integration services of citizens in Antwerp (Atlas vzw) and Ghent (IN-Gent), are crucial factors in reaching newcomers and non-native speakers in the larger cities of Flanders.

The interpretation of vulnerability and governmental responses in Germany

In **Germany**, the German federal government's initial definition (at T1) of "at-risk groups" focused on factors that increased the chance of a severe progression of COVID-19. As 2020 passed into 2021 (T2), official definitions of at-risk groups shifted to encompass factors that increased the chance of exposure to the SARS-CoV-2 virus as well. In Germany, special measures were taken to support health vulnerabilities. The broader set of governmental measures explicitly and/or implicitly targeted a wide range of population groups and institutions. These included population groups and institutions/sectors.

Specifically, the Federal Government of Germany implemented several measures regarding vulnerable groups. This response towards vulnerability was influenced by the infection fluctuation. It was mainly focused early in protecting elderly and disabled people. Later in the course of the pandemic additional groups were identified as vulnerable, such as health care workers, residents in collective accommodations, such as asylum-seekers and the homeless and low-wage and temporary-contract workers. To these groups was given priority access to vaccines. Moreover, Germany took economic and social criteria into account in including people in vulnerable groups. From an economic perspective, employers, employees in a wide range of sectors such as but not limited to cultural centers and nurses that observed economic support and a minimum wage rise, were considered vulnerable. From a social perspective, vulnerable groups were individuals that experienced domestic violence and negative psychological effects, and took measures to strengthen existing services or provide new services tailored to these groups.

In Germany, the main lesson learned is that the BMG Evaluation of the Legal Foundation and Measures of Pandemic Policies (Assessment of the Legal Foundation and of the Measures of the Pandemic Policies) criticized the lack of attention given by policymakers to certain vulnerable groups. It also identified cases where existing vulnerabilities deteriorated, or new vulnerabilities were created. According to several international studies, one of the most important effects was the psychological and social impact of the pandemic response measures on women and young people. It is therefore **recommended** to offer improved digital therapeutic resources and to ensure a minimum level of social contact. A typical example is the impact of school closures on children and young people and balances the clear evidence of these effects with the lack of decisive evidence of the effectiveness of school closures as non-pharmacological intervention. Another notable element of the evaluation is that some measures may have exacerbated the vulnerability of the sexes, confirming the importance of protecting women against domestic violence. Finally, in some cases, the pandemic seems to have led

to the 're-tradition' of gender roles and the reduction of economic gender inequality (e.g., as some financial support mechanisms seem to primarily benefit male workers).

The interpretation of vulnerability and governmental responses in Greece

In **Greece**, the governmental structure and main actors involved in the pandemic management remained the same (Kathimerini, 2021). There were minimal changes, with minimum repositioning of key decision makers, as the Government proceeded with internal restructuring of the administrative composition (To Vima, 2021). Nevertheless, those structural changes have not been observed to have a significant impact in the modus operandi of the central Government towards the society in relation to the management of the pandemic. The early implementation of measures and interventions proved effective to contain COVID-19, whereas the government demonstrated its willingness to continue to improve the healthcare systems capacity during the pandemic, which was crucial in the management of the pandemic. According to governmental officials, interviewed within the context of WP4, those efforts made to strengthen the healthcare system, and the willingness to learn from the lessons learned of other European countries, enabled Greece to evade criticism. The government invested heavily in the digitalization of the public and healthcare services, and by enhancing the cooperation through offering an active, central and leading role to healthcare scientists as crisis managers/communicators in the decision-making process. This would be achieved by establishing a national interministerial expert committee, with strictly adhering in their expert advice. The government of Greece and its response to COVID-19 has been praised by experts and other European States as effective and timely (Tubb, 2020, p.20).

A lesson learned, was that the centralized crisis management structure, together with the collaboration with the domestic scientific community, resulted in tailored interventions, that were the core elements of the Greek crisis response model. This joint response mechanism eventually compensated for the country's weaknesses, such as the local health care system's capacity (Tubb, 2020, pp. 38 – 41).

A sensitive issue for most of the interviewees was that with the pandemic the society realized new dimensions of vulnerability, and there was a need to include societal and economic vulnerabilities and groups that otherwise would not be considered as vulnerable. It was observed that government organizations addressed the need for protecting vulnerable populations on their agenda. Interviewees emphasized that a variety of initiatives took place to avoid stigmatization, targeting and further isolation of vulnerable groups (AMNA, 2022). The core element of this response was due to a constant engagement by representatives of the Ministry of Public Health, who made frequent references to vulnerable populations. Furthermore, interviewees highlighted that the government considered equality and equity when it drafted, adopted and implemented policies and measures, particularly factors such as the cost of tests, the inability to work due to COVID-19, unique characteristics of these groups based on geographic, societal and economic data, which allows for tailored measures and responses (TaxHeaven, 2022).

A lesson learned was the need to immediately address the needs of vulnerable groups within Greek society, in the pandemic period that left them exposed to the disease. The government fast and without any kind of discrimination, passed Laws and developed separate and constant programs for each group (ex. Roma, immigrants, etc.), in order to initiate a swift course of action, with the utilization of the resources of the National Public Health Organization (Stratopoulos, 2021).

Vulnerability during COVID-19 and the governmental crisis management in Italy

Initially, **Italy** was the COVID-19 epicentre of Europe, as it was one of the countries fiercely hit by the virus. From the very early stages of this unprecedented crisis, people with pre-existing medical conditions, people with disabilities and the elderly, were recognized to be at higher risk of morbidity and mortality from the virus infection from a health perspective⁸⁰. After the first early months during the implemented lockdowns, it became clear that the containment measures, which aimed to control the spread of the virus led to a profound socioeconomic crisis exacerbating pre-existing inequalities and enhancing further vulnerabilities in terms of living conditions and mental health (More in Common, 2021).

At that end, it was recognised that women suffering domestic violence, children and adolescents forced into distance learning and social isolation, people with physical and mental disabilities deprived of support from institutions other than their family network, homeless people, people in detention facilities, precarious workers, healthcare professionals, migrants and refugees were amongst the most exposed and vulnerable population groups. Specifically, in terms of social exclusion and precariousness of general living and working conditions and the existence of possible barriers in accessing healthcare services⁸¹.

Hence the Italian Government acknowledged the imperative need to protect the vulnerable groups affected by the pandemic, took immediate and executive decisions concentrating the state's efforts to tackle the emerged crisis. A series of relief measures were adopted whilst designated communication campaigns were launched concerning the people most affected by the pandemic⁸². Special telephone lines were set up for supporting women victims of domestic violence (Colagrossi et al. 2020) and targeted information campaigns and guidelines were published to facilitate and enhance the public's compliance to the applied measures. Furthermore, designated publications and online platforms were created in order to support health professionals to their work⁸³. Additional support was also given by providing necessities and equipment, organizing places for recovery and rest in the workplace as well as extra financial benefits. Regarding support, adults and children with disabilities were allocated monetary assistance and guidelines and advice were provided to caregivers⁸⁴.

Vulnerability during COVID-19 and the governmental crisis management in Portugal

Since the onset of the pandemic the **Portuguese** government acknowledged several vulnerable groups such as the elderly, people with pre-existing medical conditions, persons with disabilities, healthcare workers, homeless people and immigrants, not only from a health perspective but also considering the multiple socio-economic impact that COVID 19 had on them⁸⁵. Coordinating efforts were made to address the identified vulnerabilities and thus multi-layered policies including vaccination prioritization according to specific criteria, distribution of protective equipment to nursing homes and the expansion

⁸⁰ D4.1 Baseline report: Governmental responses, p. 55-56.

⁸¹ Supra note 80.

⁸² D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, pp 142-146.

⁸³ Ibid.

⁸⁴ D4.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts, pp. 13-32.

⁸⁵ D4.1 Baseline report: Governmental responses, p. 56.

of telemedicine services for individuals with chronic health conditions but also financial support to low-income households and people in precarious jobs, were adopted⁸⁶.

Later on and as the different waves of the pandemic evolved, additional new measures were initiated to support further the different vulnerable groups⁸⁷ such as extensive support programmes for the homeless and the asylum seekers but also children from disadvantaged backgrounds that were affected by the pandemic's impact on education.

Despite the fact that specific communications for vulnerable populations were not identified in Portugal, a campaign to promote awareness of the risks of COVID-19 among vulnerable groups and to encourage adherence to public health guidelines was launched at the governmental level⁸⁸. In addition to that, several initiatives to address the impact the pandemic had on people's mental health were deployed. At that end, civil society organisations launched campaigns to raise awareness and provide support for victims of domestic violence that emerged as a significant concern during the pandemic⁸⁹.

Overall coordinated efforts were made by the Portuguese government, public health system, civil society organisations, to acknowledge and address vulnerabilities related to various groups at different stages of the pandemic, adapting to address new vulnerabilities as they emerged.

Vulnerability during COVID-19 and the governmental crisis management in Spain

In **Spain** since the beginning of the pandemic, vulnerability was acknowledged and addressed based upon the following main criteria: (a) older population and people with previous diseases, which were identified as the most targeted groups from a health perspective and (b) regarding economic issues, people that became unemployed or under suspension of their economic activity, which were acknowledged as people that found themselves in an extremely difficult situation due to the profound socio-economic impact of the pandemic and were eligible for receiving state support⁹⁰. Furthermore, other recognised vulnerable groups included minors under the age of 14, people who required housing assistance, people that were not able to access basic food or other basic products or services, irregular migrants and women victims of gender or domestic violence⁹¹. The aforementioned definition of vulnerability and the prioritization of different vulnerable groups to receive public support have not been substantially changed during the pandemic in Spain.

Regarding the elderly and people with disabilities, designated measures were applied emphasizing to sanitary and isolation health protocols including restriction of family visits to elderly care homes and limitation of contacts between patients (Abellán et al., 2018). In addition, when the vaccination against COVID 19 commenced, these groups were given prioritization⁹² according to age and pre-existing medical conditions and thus completely vaccinated by May 2021 (Spanish Health Ministry, n.d.). From an economic perspective, the relevant support included wage replacement programmes (the ERTE programme), approval of a Minimum Living Income which entailed a universal wage for people either

⁸⁶ D4.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on governmental responses and impacts, pp. 13-32.

⁸⁷ D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, pp. 146-151.

⁸⁸ Ibid.

⁸⁹ Ibid.

⁹⁰ D4.1 Baseline report: Governmental responses, pp 57-58.

⁹¹ Ibid.

⁹² D4.5 Baseline report: Governmental responses – update M22, pp. 109-110, 151-153.

with very low salary or those unemployed⁹³. Furthermore, the state in cooperation with NGOs deployed designated programmes for food and supplies distribution to irregular migrants.

As the pandemic evolved, a growing focus on mental issues emerged⁹⁴. People that were not considered as vulnerable at earlier stages of the pandemic were identified as being significantly affected by the measures implemented to reduce the spreading of the virus in terms of the induced burden on their mental health (Pérez et al. 2022). At that end the case of young people, received more attention as the rate of suicides among young population has increased since the start of the pandemic and thus designated mental health policies have been adopted.

The interpretation of vulnerability and governmental responses in Sweden

In **Sweden**, similarly to other target countries, communication targeted both the general public and vulnerable groups. Vulnerability was identified from a multi-dimensional perspective by the PHA and included low socio-economic status citizens, migrants and the elderly in the initial phase. Vulnerability encompassed other categories as the pandemic progressed such as pregnant women, disabled, obese and chronically ill citizens. The PHA addressed crisis communication with vulnerable groups by translating relevant material in different languages and tailoring messages for different vulnerable groups in collaboration with other civil society organizations such as mosques and churches. A **good practice** identified is the multi-governance level collaboration between responsible governance entities and the appointment of key communicators who interacted with marginalized groups. The main lesson learned is the assignment of communication experts who can collaborate with regional and local authorities in order to reach out marginalised groups.

During the last phase (T2), high vaccine reluctance rates were observed with citizens of migrant backgrounds (Svt, n.d.)⁹⁵. To increase vaccination rates, the PHA and regional administrations conducted vaccination information campaigns in different languages, employed health guides and local vaccination centers outside facilities of religious importance (i.e. mosques), as well as vaccine-buses. The implementation of such measures are identified as **good practices**, since governmental officials ought to tailor the vaccination efforts in accordance with the local community characteristics while actively engaging with each target group. This approach was proven to be highly successful. Contrary to other target countries, the reasoning of the Swedish vaccination campaign was based on voluntary choice.

This approach however could also function counterproductively. This was highlighted in the Corona Commission 2020 report, which criticized governmental policies that failed to adequately protect elderly citizens, while the current and previous governments were aware of the shortcomings in such facilities. The second report (October 2021), would once again present the governmental response towards the main vulnerable group as late and insufficient⁹⁶. The Swedish government was also criticized for imprecise recommendations and advice which were left with open interpretation. The Corona Commission in the second report⁹⁷ suggested that the response mechanism led by the

⁹³ Ibid.

⁹⁴ Ibid.

⁹⁵ <https://www.svt.se/nyheter/inrikes/folkhalsomyndigheten-kritiserar-nar-utrikesfodda-halkar-efter-i-vaccineringen-detta-har-vi-varnat-om>.

⁹⁶ SOU 2021:89, Delbetänkande 2 _ Sverige under pandemin, February 2021.

⁹⁷ SOU 2021:89, Delbetänkande 2 _ Sverige under pandemin, February 2021; SOU 2022:10, Slutbetänkande – Sverige under pandemin, February 2022.

government and PHA had too few decisive actions, “too weak and too late” (ibid), while stressing the challenges of crisis management in fragmented administrative and governmental levels⁹⁸.

In conclusion, the main lessons learned is that governance levels should actively cooperate in crisis management processes, particularly in reaching out marginalized social groups whereas, responsible authorities and decision makers should adopt pre-emptive *modus operandi* particularly in relation to the protection of vulnerable groups such as the elderly. Decision makers and policy experts are **recommended** to appoint communication experts, familiar with the target groups who might be hard to reach and actively engage in dissemination activities utilising traditional and contemporary means and methods. Overall, dissemination efforts, decisions, measures and policies should be implemented in a clear manner as open interpretation may generate confusion on target audiences.

The interpretation of vulnerability and governmental responses in the UK (England & Wales)

In the **UK**, and according to the Health Protection about the Coronavirus and its Restrictions (in England), the vulnerable groups were identified as people aged 70 or older, people under 70 with an underlying health condition, as well as pregnant women (United Kingdom - Secretary of State, 2020, March 26). Homeless people were also highlighted as a high-risk group, because they were more vulnerable to COVID-19 infection. Also, people from ethnic minorities and the homeless were similarly identified as vulnerable groups. Public Health England, published an evidence report with suggestions for the central government, on how to ensure COVID-19 recovery strategies to reduce existing health inequalities, while the government announced that it would provide £1.6 billion for local authorities to respond to COVID-19 pressures, including for services helping the most vulnerable (Public Health England, 2020, June). Young people’s mental health was also addressed by the central government by funding specific charities to psychologically support children and teenagers in need. Children were also affected by the closure of schools, specifically those coming from disadvantaged families who had less access to technological means and insufficient support from their parents compared to others. However, the government, wishing to close this “disadvantage gap”, issued: assistance measures such as additional funding for 2020-2021 period, a tutoring program and enhanced support for remote learning (Government of the United Kingdom - Department of Education, 2020, November 19).

A main lesson learned identified with the UK, is that research on COVID-19 and vulnerable groups by the UK parliament website generated more results in relation to vulnerability, which provided to the central government evidence that not all people are familiar with the digital devices and do not have the necessary equipment or monetary funds to own one. Thus, the UK central government had to provide laptops to disadvantaged school children as well as training courses to improve workplace skills and agreed measures with leading telecom companies to support the vulnerable customers to pay their bills and remove caps on data allowances (Government of the United Kingdom, Department for Digital, Culture, Media & Sport and The Rt Hon Oliver Dowden CBE MP, 2020, March 29).

Separately for Wales, the local government did not create a specific plan for vulnerable people, in the beginning of the pandemic. Nonetheless, as the pandemic continued, there were multiple adaptations of measures from the government regarding vulnerable groups. These adaptations included provisions for Black, Asian, and minority ethnic (BAME) groups (Wales COVID-19 Evidence

⁹⁸ *SOU 2022:10, Slutbetänkande – Sverige under pandemin, Summary in English, February 2022, p. 24.*

Centre, June 2021), and people without sufficient resources to participate in pandemic self-governance (such as Gypsies) or unable to develop full knowledge of risks (such as people with learning disabilities).

In the case of Wales, the main lesson learned is that the lack of a holistic specific plan for all vulnerable groups, as shown in the June 2020 report published by the BAME COVID-19 Socioeconomic Subgroup, revealed with its recommendations the need to mitigate the impact of COVID-19 on certain minority ethnic groups, that were people with low income and therefore in disadvantage. This means that there were people left out from the local's governments planning, as exhibited in the November 2020 self-isolation scheme, which was issued to support people who cannot work from home and had to isolate, or the prioritized vaccination to people with learning disabilities, that took place after a recommendation from the Joint Committee on Vaccination and Immunisation (JCVI) (Wales COVID-19 Evidence Centre, June 2021).

4 Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has undeniably been a contemporary healthcare crisis for the socio-political structure and healthcare system of the European communities. To mitigate this threat, target states developed, adopted and implemented a series of measures, policies and practices, aimed at the decisive containment of the spread of the virus within their communities, developed protection protocols and countermeasures such as the COVID-19 vaccination efforts, while simultaneously examining the multi-dimensional interpretation of vulnerability and how new types of vulnerability emerged due to the consequences of COVID-19. The main objective of this deliverable is to identify and examine **good practices** and lessons learned that stem from the aforementioned governmental responses. In addition, the objective of this deliverable is to generate tailored recommendations for policy and decision makers.

In order to achieve these objectives, it was important to conduct an overview of policies and practices developed and implemented in relation to the socio-political structure and governmental response, alterations in COVID-19 related measures and policies as well as the interpretation of vulnerability from each target state.

Overall, some COVINFORM states have a fragmented administrative socio-political structure, which despite having entities of executive authority, regional and local governments and communities enjoy great autonomy. These countries are Austria, Belgium, Germany, Sweden, Spain. In addition, in comparison to the aforementioned countries, states that have a top-down approach and a central administration can be identified, such as Greece, Italy, Portugal. UK can be considered a unique case due to the nature of the group of nations socio-political modus operandi. In these states, a certain degree of autonomy lies within the regional and local administrations, nevertheless, the national government has the main role in decision and policy making.

First Pandemic Phase (T0)

During the first pandemic phase (T0), several **good practices** can be identified which mainly relate to the status of preparedness, as well as means and methods of intercepting the initial pandemic outbreak. The main lessons learned that have emerged by **good practices** are the utilization of pre-existing pandemic plans and crisis response structures, as well as the socio-political willingness to conduct pre-emptive actions in order to compensate for systemic weaknesses. In particular, most if not all target states relied on pre-existing pandemic legislations and policies such as Influenza pandemic plans, which foresaw the creation of specialised task forces and the implementation of containment measures. In addition, upon the outbreak of COVID-19, most target states activated or developed specialised scientific committees, agencies and task forces, under the supervision of the Ministries of Health, which closely cooperated with national, regional and local governments and contributed immensely to crisis monitoring and management, risk – threat analysis and the development of policies. In some cases, such as Greece, no radical adaptations or changes in the governmental structured can be observed. The lack of a clear response mechanism or a crisis management structure, was compensated by socio-political willingness as Greece retained the centralised, top-down approach, and issued a plethora (800) legislative Acts. Greece declared a state of emergency, by pre-emptively implementing curfews and other movement restriction measures. On the other hand, in Italy, in spite the existence of pre-pandemic plans, procedures were ignored, and COVID-19 had a radical progression at the initial phase, contributing to substantial governmental structural changes.

A State of Emergency was declared in Spain, Greece, Italy and Portugal, which allowed extended legislative and executive powers to national governments. In some cases, such as in Italy, experienced structural changes, while Greece, Spain and Portugal, retained the socio-political structure with minimum changes. Another important lesson learnt, as can be identified whilst examining target states with fragmented administrative modus operandi, were the challenges that governments faced in relation to the development, drafting and implementation of policies and measures, as well as the identification of administrative boundaries among the different levels of governance. In most target states, such as the UK and Sweden among others, confusion, communication and cooperation challenges can be observed due to unclear administrative boundaries and blurry areas of responsibility. These challenges can be severely counterproductive during the process of intercepting and mitigating the consequences of a healthcare crisis.

Decision and policy makers are **recommended** to engage in realistic, scenario-based simulation activities which would thoroughly examine the status of preparedness, expose systemic and organisational weaknesses, generate potential policies, practices and processes to counter and mitigate the consequences of contemporary health crises. Moreover, decision makers and policy makers are **recommended** to re-examine pre-existing pandemic plans and incorporate the lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic, in order to refurbish and modernize administrative, governmental responses, based on the unique characteristics of each target state. Further, during crises, decision and policy makers are highly **recommended** to incorporate the valuable contribution of the scientific and academic community, as well as the experience of practitioners and on-site experts. To increase the effectiveness, efficiency and generate realistic responses, when drafting policies, implementing practices and governmental responses ought to take into consideration both scientific, academic, practitioner and on-site expert opinions, which are based on experience, academic background and expertise.

Second and Third Pandemic Phase (T1 & T2)

Several lessons learned and **good practices** can be identified also during the second and third phase of the COVID-19 pandemic (T1 & T2). Most if not all target states implemented non-pharmaceutical interventions and rolled out a vaccination campaign, nevertheless, in some cases these interventions had a stricter character such as in Greece with the imposition of fines for citizens that violated the implemented policies, in contrast with the case of Sweden, in which policies were of a more voluntary nature due to legislative limitations. One lesson learned is that non-pharmaceutical interventions should not be prolonged for extended periods of time, while simultaneously, decision makers and policy experts are **recommended** to conduct multi-level evaluations of the health, socio-political, legal, economic and cultural consequences containment measures can have on the general population and the vulnerable groups. Based on the interviews conducted within the context of WP4, in countries such as Greece, in which prolonged lockdowns were implemented, the negative psychological impact of this measure was apparent within the general population and in vulnerable groups such as children (UNICEF, 2022).

In most cases, governmental responses were based on specific policies and practices, which in most target states were evaluated based on the effectiveness and efficiency they introduced whilst mitigating the negative consequences of the pandemic. The main lesson learned for the second and third pandemic phase (T1 - T2), which is a **recommended** process for decision and policy makers, is the imperative need to revise and thoroughly examine the effectiveness, efficiency, both intended and unintended impacts, crisis related policies and practices may have for both the general public and vulnerable populations. Constructive criticism should be taken into consideration as it can lead to the necessary adjustment of policies and practices, nevertheless, to do so, another lesson learned that stems from a **good practice**, is to emphasize on clear risk communication mechanisms and encourage open, unbiased, democratic dialogue between governmental actors who are **recommended** to constantly engage with regional and local communities. The Epidemic law of Austria which has not been brought up to date for almost 70 years, even though it has been utilised as a reference point to a certain percentage, is another example of the imperative need to frequently update pre-existing pandemic plans. Expert interviews also highlighted the importance of having multipolar discussion panels, which encourage citizen engagement in expressing their voices.

In addition, another **good practice** identified in most target states is the utilisation of a colour based risk indicator system, which was part of the risk analysis mechanism, based on the infection rates in each region and/or local community. Decision makers and policy experts are **recommended** to continuously monitor the progression of a crisis, which may introduce fluctuations in the intensity of casualty and spread. According to the progression of a crisis, administrative authorities can re-evaluate and implement more tailored responses, which can include the introduction of targeted measures, disengagement from specific measures and emphasis in recovery strategies. Therefore, another lesson learned which stem from a **good practice**, which is simultaneously highly **recommended**, is the development of a recovery strategy, which takes into consideration the health, legal, socio-political, economic and cultural, consequences of the pandemic and the impacts of implemented policies and practices, in order to develop a disengagement and recovery strategy. Similarly, to T0, in some cases such as Belgium, the fragmented nature of the governmental administrative approach, impacted the effectiveness rate of the responses and generated confusion between administrative entities and the general population. Decision makers and policy experts are **recommended** to actively develop a transparent, easy to comprehend strategy, which would be communicated in a clear manner to citizens

and incorporate distinct phases (short, medium and long-term) in mitigating and recovering from the consequences of a health crisis.

Vulnerability

In relation to vulnerability, most if not all target states, did not adopt an encompassing interpretation which predominantly focused on health considerations during the first pandemic phase (T0). This gradually changed as more data and extensive knowledge was acquired through observation, research and analysis. In relation to how the COVID-19 pandemic impacted various socio-demographic groups, new vulnerabilities emerged and were identified by governmental response mechanisms of the aforementioned target states. **Good practices** include cooperation with grassroots initiatives and NGOs to compensate systemic weaknesses and lack of capacity, the development and implementation of tailored responses to mitigate the consequences of the pandemic in vulnerable groups such as elderly citizens, citizens with chronic diseases, employees and employers who were negatively impacted by COVID-19, children, single parent families, marginalised groups such as homeless citizens, refugees and migrants, drug addicts, ethnic and religious minorities among other vulnerable groups. These responses included financial compensation and economic mitigation measures such as COVID-19 related benefits, vouchers to ensure that children had the proper means to conduct their school classes virtually, sheltering, healthcare and basic needs provision to marginalised groups and citizens living in extreme or borderline poverty, implementation of regulations and restrictions in relation to visitations in elderly care facilities among other tailored responses. Decision and policy makers are **recommended** to constantly evaluate the landscape of the pandemic with the accompanying consequences and impacts which stem from policies and practices, conduct frequent re-evaluation, engage and facilitate open dialogue with the local and regional communities to better understand how a health crisis has influenced the living conditions of the target populations. Concluding, COVID-19 has taught the governmental mechanism and contemporary communities how important scientific expertise, multi societal level engagement and clear risk communication, tailored policies and practices, evaluation and risk assessment processes, identification of the multidimensional interpretation of vulnerability, vaccination efforts and awareness raising campaigns can be whilst combating unprecedented healthcare challenges on the scale of a worldwide pandemic.

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Annex 1: Government outcome indicators for the COVINFORM target countries from 2019-2021.

	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021
	AUSTRIA			BELGIUM			GERMANY			GREECE			ITALY		
Migrant population ¹	1.2	1.2	-	1.3	1.0	-	1.1	0.9	-	1.2	0.8	-	0.6	0.4	-
Age ²															
<i>Under 20</i>	19.4	19.3	19.3	22.4	22.4	22.3	18.4	18.4	18.4	19.4	19.4	19.3	18.0	17.8	17.7
<i>Over 65</i>	18.8	19.0	19.2	18.9	19.1	19.3	21.5	21.8	22.0	22.0	22.3	22.5	22.9	23.2	23.5
<i>20-65</i>	66.8	66.7	66.7	64.0	63.9	63.9	65.8	65.7	65.5	64.2	64.0	63.9	64.9	64.8	64.6
Women (%) ³	50.8	50.8	50.8	50.7	50.7	50.7	50.7	50.7	50.7	51.4	51.3	51.3	51.3	51.3	51.3
GDP (EUR) ⁴	38110	35390	36920	36080	33870	35850	35980	34310	35290	17760	16180	17590	27230	24900	26700
Housing overcrowding ⁵	10.0	8.4	9.8	3.1	3.2	2.9	6.1	7.8	7.6	14.0	14.0	13.4	17.2	15.3	15.3
Trust in government ⁶	50.0	59.0	41.5	35.5	30.0	41.0	47.5	61.0	52.0	23.5	35.0	27.0	27.5	29.0	32.0
Unemployment ⁷	2.9	3.4	3.9	3.0	3.1	3.5	2.1	2.5	2.3	9.6	8.9	8.0	5.4	4.9	5.0
Living in poverty ⁸	13.3	13.9	14.7	14.8	14.1	13.1	14.8	16.1	-	17.9	17.7	-	20.1	20	-
Income inequality ⁹	4.2	4.1	4.1	3.6	3.7	3.4	4.9	4.9	-	5.1	5.2	-	6.0	5.8	-
Disposable Income ¹⁰	40066	39852	41859	38141	39526	40779	42753	43760	44444	22825	22157	23879	33054	33047	34227
Reduced income ¹⁰	1.16	-3.06	1.73	2.08	0.8	0.9	0.81	0.91	-0.42	4.04	-1.26	-	0.37	-1.85	2.37
Food insecurity ¹¹	3.0	3.3	-	3.7	4.8	-	3.4	3.5	-	8.6	6.8	-	6.7	6.3	-
Social protection ¹²	28.6	-	-	27.4	-	-	28.9	32.0	-	24.8	-	-	28.3	33.3	-
Economic interventions ¹³	-	0.27	0.29	-	0.55	0.71	-	0.53	0.71	-	0.49	0.57	-	0.42	0.57

(-)Missing data/not applicable.

¹Reported as Annual Immigration Rate (%). Data source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/migr_imm9ctz.²Reported as Population on 1 January by age group (%). Data source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/demo_r_piangerp3.³Reported as Population on 1 January by sex (%). Data Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/demo_pjan.⁴Reported as Real GDP per capita in Euro. Data Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/sdg_08_10.⁵Reported as Overcrowding rate by household type (%) - EU-SILC survey. Data Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/tessi175>.⁶Reported as, "How much trust do you have in national government?" (%). Data source: <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/browse/all/series/4961>.⁷Reported as unemployment rate per capita (%). Data Source: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/lfsa_ugad.⁸Reported as "At-risk-of-poverty rate" (%). Data Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/tespm010>.⁹Reported as Inequality of income distribution (%). Data Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-datasets/-/tespm151>.¹⁰Reported as Gross per capita household disposable income (EUR) and percent change (%). Data source: <https://data.oecd.org/hha/household-disposable-income.htm>.¹¹Defined as Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population (%). Data source: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/FS>.¹²Reported as Rate of total expenditure on social protection benefits (%). https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/spr_exp_sum/default/table?lang=en¹³Reported as Intensity of economic interventions in response to COVID-19 pandemic (0-1). Data source: <https://response2covid19.org/>.

Annex 1: Government outcome indicators for the COVINFORM target countries from 2019-2021.

	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021	2019	2020	2021
	PORTUGAL			SPAIN			SWEDEN			UK		
Migrant population	0.7	0.7	-	1.6	1.0	-	1.1	0.8	-	1.0	-	-
Age ¹⁴												
<i>Under 20</i>	19.1	18.9	18.6	19.7	19.6	19.4	23.3	23.3	23.3	17.9	17.9	17.7
<i>Over 65</i>	21.8	22.1	22.4	19.4	19.6	19.8	19.9	20.0	20.1	18.5	18.6	18.8
<i>20-65</i>	65.1	65.0	65.0	66.0	66.0	66.1	62.2	62.0	61.8	63.6	63.5	63.5
Women (%) ¹⁵	52.8	52.8	52.8	51.0	51.0	51.0	49.7	49.7	49.7	50.6	50.6	50.6
GDP (EUR) ¹⁶	18670	17070	17920	25200	22350	23510	44180	42910	44840	33763	30504	32555
Housing overcrowding ¹⁷	3.4	3.1	4.4	2.6	2.7	3.0	10.0	10.8	14.7	3.0	-	-
Trust in government	44.0	52.0	48.0	23.0	25.0	21.0	57.0	62.0	56.0	20.0	34.0	41.5
Unemployment ¹⁸	4.1	4.3	4.1	8.6	9.2	9.0	4.6	5.6	6.0	3.8	4.6	4.5
Living in poverty ¹⁹	17.2	16.2	-	20.7	21	21.7	17.1	16.1	15.7	17.9	15.8	16.6
Income inequality	5.2	5.0	-	5.9	5.8	6.2	4.3	4.1	4.0	5.8	5.9	6.3
Disposable Income	27747	27334	28157	29805	28802	29548	35688	35648	36836	34823	34909	36891
Reduced income	3.74	-1.84	2.44	3.09	-2.5	1.01	0.99	-0.87	3.59	1.55	-1.7	0.79
Food insecurity	11.5	11.6	-	8.8	8.6	-	5.3	5.3	-	3.9	3.5	-
Social protection ²⁰	23.1	26.5	-	23.7	-	-	27.1	28.7	-	17.5	14.3	15.0
Economic interventions	-	0.56	0.71	-	0.67	0.86	-	0.48	0.51	-	0.68	0.86

(-)Missing data/not applicable.

¹⁴UK only. Reported as Age groups in proportion to total population (%). Data source: <https://data.oecd.org/pop/working-age-population.htm#indicator-chart/>.

¹⁵UK only. National mid-year population estimates for the UK and its constituent countries (%). Data source:

<https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationestimates/datasets/populationestimatesforukenglandandwalesscotlandandnorthernireland>.

¹⁶UK only. GDP per capita (GBP). Data source: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/grossdomesticproductgdp/timeseries/ihxw/pn2#othertimeseries>.

¹⁷UK only. Prevalence of Household overcrowding (%). Data source: <https://www.ethnicity-facts-figures.service.gov.uk/housing/housing-conditions/overcrowded-households/latest#download-the-data>.

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¹⁹UK only. Reported as households below the average income. Data source: <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/households-below-average-income-for-financial-years-ending-1995-to-2021>.

²⁰UK only. Reported as the proportion of total expenditure spent on social protection benefits (%). Data source: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/benefit-expenditure-and-caseload-tables-2022>.